

Roadmaps, White Paper and Value Added Reports v3

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Executive Summary

This report is the number three (*v3*) in the EU-CIP project's ongoing series of Roadmaps, White Papers, and Value-Added Reports, offering a comprehensive update on the state of Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) across Europe.

Building on previous analyses, this edition provides a concise overview of the latest technologies, techniques, and tools that can address identified capability gaps within the CIP/CIR landscape. It incorporates updated insights based on new research and stakeholder feedback, ensuring that the recommendations remain relevant and actionable.

Key features of this report include:

- **Clear Objectives and Methodology:** The report introduces quantifiable objectives for the roadmap and outlines the methodology used to evaluate and synthesize information gathered to date.
- **Action Plan for Capability Gaps:** A strategic action plan is proposed to address current gaps in CIP/CIR, guiding stakeholders on how to achieve and sustain secure deployment, operation, and service provision.
- **Technology Landscape:** The report presents a rich portfolio of state-of-the-art technologies—ranging from networking (e.g., 5G/6G, cloud/edge) and data/AI solutions to advanced cybersecurity tools. It highlights how these technologies can be clustered and integrated to boost preparedness, facilitate effective response, and support regulatory compliance, such as with the CER Directive.
- **Skills and Training:** Recognizing that technology alone is not enough, the report identifies essential skills profiles and training needs required to fill capability gaps, aligning with the project's broader focus on workforce development.
- **Market and Sector Insights:** The analysis includes recent market trends and sector-specific insights, drawing on a series of white papers that explore CIP/CIR challenges and solutions in key sectors such as finance and space. These white papers, accessible through the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub, are integral to the project's commitment to knowledge sharing and sectoral relevance.
- **Standards and Best Practices:** The importance of existing and emerging standards is emphasized, alongside complementary assets such as training and skills development, to ensure a holistic approach to CIP/CIR advancement.

This report is part of a regularly updated series, produced every six months, that supports the EU-CIP Knowledge Hub and informs the next phase of the project. Each edition builds on the last, refining the roadmap, updating capability needs, and deepening sectoral insights to provide stakeholders with the latest intelligence and strategic foresight.

By delivering these ongoing, value-added insights, the EU-CIP project empowers policymakers, industry leaders, and practitioners to make informed decisions, drive innovation, and strengthen the resilience and security of Europe's critical infrastructures.

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Definitions and acronyms

2D	2 Dimensional
3D	3 Dimensional
5G	Fifth generation technology standard for cellular networks
6G	Sixth generation technology standard for wireless communications
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	American Petroleum Institute
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
AR	Augmented Reality
ARIMA	AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Averages
ASME	American Society of Mechanical Engineers
BCDR	Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery
BMI	Bundesministerium des Inneren (English: German Ministry of the Interior)
BSI	Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik (English: Federal Office for Information Security)
BYOD	Bring Your Own Device
CBRN	Chemical, Biological, Radiological, and Nuclear
CCTV	Closed-Circuit TeleVision
CE	Critical Entity
CE-CISE	Customs Extended Common Information Sharing Environment
CEN	Comité Européen de Normalisation (English: European Committee for Standardization)
CER	Critical Entities Resilience
CG1-22	Capability Gap No. 1-22
CI	Critical Infrastructure
CIP	Critical Infrastructure Protection
CIPRNET	Critical Infrastructures Preparedness and Resilience Research Network
CIR	Critical Infrastructure Resilience
CISA	Cybersecurity & Infrastructure Security Agency
CISCO	Computer Information System Company
CIWIN	Critical Infrastructure Warning Information Network
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
COIN	Context, Observation, Impact, and Next steps
COVID19	COroNoVIrus Desease 2019
CPS	Cyber-Physical Systems
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
CSIM	Converged Security Information Management
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DG	Directorate General
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DIN	Deutsche Industrie Norm (English: German Industrial Standard)
DRS	Disaster-Resilient Society
DS	Data Spaces
DSS	Decision Support System
DT	Digital Twin

DWC	Digital Water City
EC	European Commission
ECSCI	European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures
EDXL	Emergency Data Exchange Language
ELK	Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana
EN	European Standard (Euronorm)
EPCIP	European Program for Critical Infrastructure Protection
ERNICIP	European Reference Network for Critical Infrastructure Protection
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
FEMA	Federal Emergency Management Agency
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GOPP	Goal Oriented Project Planning
GTZ	Gesellschaft für Technische Zusammenarbeit (English: Society for Technical Cooperation)
HAZUS	Hazards United States
HIL	Human In the Loop
HPC	High-Performance Computation
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IBM	International Business Machines Corporation
ICS	Industrial Control Systems
ICT	Information Communication Technologies
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, Inc.
IP	Intellectual Property
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
JESIP	Joint Emergency Service Interoperability Programme
LFA	Logical Framework Approach
ML	Machine Learning
NIS, NIS2	Directive on security of network and information systems
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OpenVAS	Open Vulnerability Assessment Scanner
OPSWAT	Omni-Platform Security With Access Technologies
OT	Operational Technology
RAET	Risk Analysis and Evaluation Toolkit
RAND	Research ANd Development
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SDO	Standards Developing Organization
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SOC	Security Operations Centre
TC	Technical Committee
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment

TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facilities
TEF	The Trusted Exchange Framework
TEM	Threats and Exposures Management
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
TS	Technical Specification
TTP	Tactics, Techniques, and Procedures
UAS	Unmanned Aerial Systems
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
UNDRR	United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
US	United States
USA	United States of America
USAID	US Agency for International Development
USD	US Dollar
VAS	Vulnerability Assessment Scanner
WEF	World Economic Forum
XAI	Explainable AI
XG	Ten Gigabit
ZOPP	ZielOrientierte ProjektPlanung (English: Goal Oriented Project Planning)

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the Roadmap

The EU-CIP roadmap series is designed to advance Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR) across Europe. In an increasingly interconnected world facing evolving threats, safeguarding critical infrastructure is essential for societal stability, security, and prosperity.

This roadmap series envisions a future where critical infrastructure protection is intelligent, automated, predictive, and collaborative. It addresses new challenges such as asymmetric, hybrid, and cyber-physical attacks, as well as vulnerabilities arising from shifting geopolitical and technological landscapes. While the roadmap recommends a range of individual measures and activities, it also emphasizes their integration to achieve a comprehensive vision for CIP.

This edition highlights state-of-the-art technologies, methods, and tools that can help close identified capability gaps. The roadmap aims to:

- Enhance security
- Foster collaboration
- Ensure compliance with regulations and standards
- Accelerate innovation
- Enable strategic allocation of resources

Resilience is the cornerstone of critical infrastructure's ability to withstand and recover from disruptions—whether caused by natural disasters, technological failures, or malicious acts. The roadmap series is focused on minimizing disruption and enabling rapid recovery.

To strengthen security, the roadmap identifies vulnerabilities across critical infrastructure sectors and proposes measures to address both physical and cyber risks. Effective CIP and CIR require cooperation among governments, regulators, private sector entities, and international partners. Promoting partnerships and information sharing enhances awareness, coordinates responses, and leverages collective expertise.

Compliance with regulations, standards, and best practices is central to effective protection and resilience. The roadmap provides guidance to help stakeholders understand and meet these requirements.

Innovation is key to meeting new threats and adapting to emerging challenges. The roadmap encourages the adoption of innovative technologies and processes, as well as research initiatives to address future vulnerabilities. Given limited resources, strategic allocation is essential. The roadmap explores risk-based decision-making, cost-effective solutions, and maximizing the impact of investments to achieve tangible improvements in security and resilience.

Overall, the roadmap series aims to build a secure, resilient, and sustainable critical infrastructure ecosystem that can meet the challenges of the 21st century and support the needs of society and the economy.

Note that several of the resources and content referenced in the scope of the document are available through the project's knowledge hub at: <https://knowledgehub.eucip.eu/>.

1.2. Quantifiable Objectives of the Roadmap

Since late 1980's vast majority of all EU projects and related activities follows the Goal Oriented Project Planning (GOPP), introduced on the basis of the German ZOPP approach (Zielorientierte Projektplanung, in German, initially used and promoted by the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Technische Zusammenarbeit GTZ - German Technical Cooperation).

The approach provides a systematic structure for identification, planning, and management of projects primarily relying on the GOPP logical project framework (initially called the "Logical Framework Approach (LFA)" when developed for the US Agency for International Development (USAID) in the 1960s). This approach summarizes and structures the main elements of a project and highlights logical linkages between intended inputs, planned activities and expected results. All the templates for different EU projects are based on this approach, mostly without making a direct reference to it, including the templates used in the Disaster-Resilient Societies (DRS) and Critical Infrastructure Protection (INFRA) series of projects, and for the EU-CIP project, too. In other words, GOPP/LFA approach is a common denominator for all the project-like activities in the EU.

Consequently, understanding the EU-Roadmaps as blueprints for future projects, the roadmaps produced in the EU-CIP project – including this roadmap – have all the reasons to follow the GOPP as this will make them more compatible and better aligned with the well-adopted practice, while ensuring and enhancing consistency of the own roadmap producing process.

The four GOPP main principles (participants, problem, objectives, alternatives) "translate" thus in the following main questions to be addressed by this roadmap:

1. The Roadmap for whom?
2. The Roadmap to where? What's the destination? Which problem will be solved once the roadmap is implemented?
3. The Roadmap for which trip? What are the waypoints on the trip (specific objectives, time plan)?
4. The resources needed for the Roadmap? Alternatives underway?

The above questions will be answered in detail later in the project. Here, profound estimations of possible answers are provided, which will be sharpened and facilitated in the upcoming roadmap documents (v4-v6).

1.2.1. The Roadmap for whom

General: The participation analysis should provide an overview of persons, groups, organisations connected to the roadmap, as well as their interests, motives, users' stakes, and implications for their future work. This should be supported by analytical and graphical components (e.g., charts, business intelligence, etc.).

Project's approach: EU-CIP intends to use a CRM-like (Customer-Relationship-Management) system as described above. The planning for this CRM system will be provided in upcoming documents of the roadmap series (v4-v6).

In practical terms it means that when this roadmap tackles the “state-of-the-art technologies, techniques, methods and tools that can contribute to fill the identified capability gaps” one must be able to attribute and quantify its relevance for certain groups of roadmap users.

E.g., if the roadmap proposes to

"promote development and use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in physical protection systems at airports in the EU",

it is evident to also assess how many airport users will be affected and involve them in a representative way in the definition of the roadmap and in its implementation.

The same approach will be applied to future roadmaps which have these different focuses:

- V4: Aggregated and consolidated view of outcomes (including on technological, industrial, legal and ethical issues), future trends, lessons learnt and best practices derived from past and current security research projects.
- V5: A Common and updated map of opportunities and constraints for the exploitation of EU security research and innovation projects, with special focus on industrialisation, commercialisation, adoption, and deployment of innovative solutions in response to common capability gaps.
- V6: Common and updated map of areas requiring standardised solutions and/or certification schemes to foster innovation uptake and market creation.

1.2.2. The Roadmap to where? What's the destination? Which problem will be solved once the roadmap is implemented?

This step includes problem analysis: major problems grouped into a problem-tree with cause and effect and identification of the core problem, as an essential basis for defining main objectives. The lowest level problems tackled by the roadmap - one at a time - should be aggregated into groups and structured as a hierarchy. Beyond defining the intended objectives of the roadmap in general terms the generic goals need to be defined more precisely throughout the series of roadmaps.

E.g. if the roadmap proposes to

"...enhance security..."

it also needs to indicate

- How big is the envisaged "enhancement" (e.g. 23%)?
[step 1 of GOPP implemented].
- Through which steps will it be achieved?
[steps 2-4 of GOPP implemented].
- What uncertainties (risks) may be encountered and how to mitigate them?
[step 5 of GOPP implemented].
- How it will be (possibly independently) measured (e.g. indicators)?
- By whom?
- When will the goal be achieved?

These items will be elaborated on in the subsequent roadmap series (v4-v6).

1.2.3. Roadmap for which trip? What are the waypoints (objectives and timeline)?

In order to lead the users to the foreseen “destination”, the roadmap should possibly define:

- The waypoints on the trip – the intermediate goals and checkpoints, at which, if needed, one re-analyse the objectives or restate them.
- The alternatives related to resources, feasibility, cost-benefit ratio, secondary (e.g. social) risks, time horizon, sustainability, and others factors.
- External resources and advisory support (e.g. an International Advisory Board).

1.3. Scope

This roadmap provides an aggregated and consolidated view of the latest technologies, techniques, methods and tools that can help close the identified capability gaps in CIP/CIR and aims to address the multi-layered challenges associated with improving the protection and resilience of critical infrastructure. It covers different sectors such as energy, transport, communications, water supply and healthcare and considers their interdependencies and the cascading effects of disruptions.

To achieve an adequate oversight and foster the foresight, EU-CIP settles a methodological framework which considers the needed data base and spans the evaluation of technologies from state-of-the-art over emerging ones and includes surveys on supporting R&I activities.

1.4. Relationship to previous Roadmaps

To provide a comprehensive and up-to-date overview of Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience (CIP/CIR), the EU-CIP project is producing a series of six roadmap documents. Each document contributes unique insights and guidance toward enhancing the protection and resilience of critical infrastructures.

The initial roadmap laid the foundation by introducing the project’s scope and identifying an initial set of capability needs and gaps. The subsequent roadmap built upon this by offering an aggregated and consolidated view of these needs and gaps, along with preliminary elements of strategies to address them.

These earlier reports serve as key inputs to the current roadmap, which focuses on presenting initial insights into the research and technological developments aimed at closing the identified gaps.

2. Methodology

EU-CIP applies a methodology for collecting and analysing data from critical infrastructures, which will continually collect, analyse, curate, extract and present information and insights about critical infrastructure protection/critical infrastructure resilience (CIP/CIR). The information to be collected and analysed will be mainly focused on: (i) cyber security research activities and outcomes for CIP/CIR, (ii) CIP/CIR with emphasis on advanced technologies, (iii) CIP/CIR policies at regional, national and EU levels, and (iv) standards from Standards Development Organizations (SDOs). The project's monitoring infrastructure will be based on: (i) standard-based data collection and continuous desk research methodology (ii) real-time observatory for CIP/CIR data, (iii) Mechanisms for the validation of the findings based on external feedback from user groups and other stakeholders, including external users of advisory board groups.

The project is designing and establishing advanced analytical capabilities for extracting foresight and insights about gaps in current knowledge and solutions, technologies that address these gaps, research outcomes and practices, legal and ethical issues, and best practices from past projects, sector-specific and region-specific aspects. The collection and analysis of information will be based on the following more specific measures: (i) continuous desk research, (ii) internal consultation with relevant stakeholders, (iii) external consultation with relevant stakeholders, (iv) open calls for engagement in consultation and findings validation, (v) findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable (fair) data observatory of research outcomes, technologies, policies, and standards, (vi) value-added reports, white papers and other knowledge assets, and (vii) data driven policy recommendations which are detailed in the ensuing sections.

2.1. Methodological Framework

EU-CIP data collection methodology and observatory provide aggregated and consolidated information on state-of-art technologies, techniques, methods and tools including data collection and analysis of research project's outcomes, leveraging on the more than 40 projects of the European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI) cluster. In line with this objective the EU-CIP project developed an automated data collection and desk research methodology shown in Figure 1. This methodology is a continuous method of collating and synthesizing existing secondary data using both qualitative and quantitative research methods from various relevant sources, an initial process for desk research. Using this methodology EU-CIP conducts regular desk research on related research outcomes, R&I projects, technologies, standards, and policies to be up to date with related developments, while having a continuous stream of information for further analysis and curation.

Figure 1: EU-CIP Automated Data Collection and Desk Research Methodology: Contributors: ENG, NRS, INNOV, EU-VRI.

The methodology consists of six activities, which are explained in the following sections.

2.1.1. Identify Research Topics

This first activity identifies what information is to be collected. For identifying CIP/CIR research topics, the foremost step is to pinpoint the specific area or subject to be surveyed. The identified topics need to have a clear research purpose to get specific insights for decision-making, understanding market trends, or exploring specific critical sectors. For EU-CIP, some potential research topics are identified as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Potential Research Topics for CIP/CIR

2.1.2. Collect Raw Data

This second activity is concerned with a consideration of a variety of information collection modalities such as desk research, interviews with sector specific consortium stakeholders, questionnaires on specific topics, workshops, and further secondary research based on proper curation of the collected data. The information to be collected is mainly focused on (i) security research activities and outcomes for CIP/CIR infrastructures, (ii) security solutions and technologies for CIP/CIR infrastructures with emphasis on cutting edge technologies that advance the state of the art and fill-in existing gaps in CIP/CIR infrastructures, (iii) security and infrastructure resilience policies, and (iv) related standards in collaboration with standards development organisations. This is achieved through 1) internal consultation with EU-CIP partners from different CIP/CIR stakeholders, 2) external consultation with advisory board members and ECSCI members obtaining feedback about data collection and desk research findings and their usability for developing policies, technologies, and standards, and 3) consultation with open call winners for engaging them in data collection and ensuring their active engagement and commitment.

2.1.3. Analyse collected Data

This third activity leverages methodologies and best practices for analysis of collected data such as the adoption of the [COIN](#) (Context, Observation, Impact, and Next steps) methodology. This can be

used to extract data-driven insights and composite policy indicators for policy makers in different areas, and tools for continuous desk research for conducting systematic desk research about CIP/CIR technologies, research initiatives, standards, and policies. For this purpose, different data sources can be utilised including research projects and their outcomes, standardization bodies, CIP/CIR research literature, technology reviews and research reports, and market analysis reports. The relevant reports will integrate the findings in the EU-CIP observatory and Knowledge Hub and the findings will be validated through EU-CIP open call winners by engaging different stakeholders. The collected data will be classified in different ways such as policies, gaps, needs, and technology analysis in the EU-CIP FAIR Data Observatory which can further be used for different analyses by multiple stakeholders to facilitate its discovery, curation, repurposing and reuse by other parties both within and outside the EU-CIP community.

2.1.4. Curate collected Data

This fourth activity is responsible for proper curation of collected data from CIP/CIR by creating, organizing and maintaining data to support decision-making, academic needs, and scientific research. The main objective of this stage is to make data findable, accessible, traceable, and classifiable. For EU-CIP, curation of collected data involves the following steps i) classifying the data into relevant CIP/CIR themes or topics to give a systematic overview of data, ii) quality control to ensure that reliable and authoritative sources are used for data collection which will be useful to identify any discrepancies, iii) data representation process which may include graphs, charts and videos to provide meaningful ways to understand the information, and iv) ethical considerations to ensure the privacy concerns and avoid sharing sensitive data to unauthorised personals.

2.1.5. Extract Relevant Information and Insights

This fifth activity facilitates the extraction of the collected data from CIP/CIR to give meaningful foresight and insights by applying different techniques such as statistics, data visualization, and software tools for identifying patterns, trends, correlations and legal and ethical issues. For CIP/CIR, it is necessary to extract insights about gaps in current knowledge and solutions, technologies that can address these gaps, research outcomes and practices that can be employed. For EU-CIP, it is important to get insights about recent trends and evolving technologies of CIP/CIR which can be ensured via quantitative and qualitative analysis. Another important aspect for EU-CIP can be to contextualize and interpret from collected data how external factors may affect the CIP/CIR, and what can be potential insights which play a significant role in protecting critical sectors.

2.1.6. Present Relevant Information and Insights

This final sixth activity presents the extracted information and insights from the collected data in a concise, neat and clean way. Although different formats such as a dashboard, a report, or a live demo can be selected for this purpose, data visualization seems to be a powerful tool. This practice can be useful for identifying relevant patterns and key results for comparing different critical scenarios and their applicability for CIP/CIR sectors. The insights will be disseminated through “Value-Added Reports, White Papers and other Knowledge Assets” to proper stakeholders which give aggregated

and consolidated view of (i) the capability needs and gaps in CIP/CIR; (ii) the state-of-the-art CIP/CIR technologies, techniques, methods and tools, (iii) outcomes, future trends, lessons learnt and best practices; (iv) mapping opportunities and gaps for the exploitation of EU CIP/CIR projects, (v) mapping of areas requiring standardised solutions to foster innovation uptake and market creation. The FAIR data observatory and Knowledge Hub which integrates stakeholders' domain knowledge will facilitate the extraction of these reports. EU-CIP will provide "Data Driven Policy and Standards Development Recommendations" based on the extracted foresight and insight, and the value-added reports.

2.2. Structured Data Collection Sources

2.2.1. Sector Wise Data Sources

Data should be collected sector-wise for deep insights into market trends in CIP/CIR, market analysis, gaps in current knowledge and limitations of current systems (e.g. what is missing in terms of R&D, which research directions must be pursued), and strengthen CIP/CIR and address limitation of current systems (e.g., asymmetric attacks, hybrid (cyber/physical) environments, terrorism threats, etc.). The identified [Critical Infrastructure Sectors](#) include:

- **Energy:** Oil and gas production, refining, treatment and storage, including pipelines, Electricity generation, Transmission of electricity, gas and oil, and Distribution of electricity, gas and oil.
- **Health:** Medical and hospital care, Medicines, serums, vaccines and pharmaceuticals, Bio-laboratories and bio-agents.
- **Information Communication Technologies (ICT):** Information system and network protection, Instrumentation automation and control systems (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) etc.), Internet, Provision of fixed telecommunications, Provision of mobile telecommunications, Radio communication and navigation, Satellite communication, and Broadcasting.
- **Transport and Traffic:** Road transport, Rail transport, Air traffic, Inland waterways transport, Ocean and short-sea shipping.
- **Media and Culture:** broadcasting (television and radio), printed and electronic press, cultural assets, highly symbolic buildings.
- **Water:** Provision of drinking water, Control of water quality, Stemming and control of water quantity.
- **Finance and insurance:** Payment services/payment structures (private), government financial assignment, insurance companies, stock exchanges.
- **Space:** Satellites and ground stations are recognised as pivotal components that need protection against disruptions and threats.
- **Food:** Provision of food and safeguarding food safety and security.
- **Municipal waste disposal:** waste from households, commerce and trade, office buildings, institutions and small businesses, yard and garden waste, street sweepings, litter containers, and market cleansing waste.
- **State and administration:** Maintaining public & legal order, safety and security, Administration of justice and detention.

The mapping of the sectors above with EU-CIP partners' contributions includes ICT (INNOV-Acts, NRS), financial and insurance (GFT, INNOV-Acts, NRS), energy (EDF), space (ENG), transport and traffic (DLR), and water (SINTEF).

Other critical infrastructures sectors (stated also in CER Directive) will follow, such as state and administration, municipal waste disposal, media and culture, health and food which need to be covered by EU-CIP partners and beyond.

2.2.2. Other Sources of Knowledge

Other sources of knowledge include journals, magazines, web sites, blogs etc. that can be consulted regularly to update the research findings. The procedure to search records initiates by asking a query from different databases to acquire available articles in the research domain of CIP/CIR. The query can be entered into the search field of relevant online databases (Table 1) and CIP/CIR Journals (Table 2). An example of the search query for this task is given below:

("security" OR "secure") AND ("cyber" AND "critical" AND "infrastructures") AND ("resilience" OR "resilient " OR "CIR") AND ("protection" OR "protecting" OR "CIP")

Table 1: Online Databases

Data base name	Description	Access link	EU-CIP activity
ACM Digital Library	A collection of publications, including journals, conference proceedings, and magazines.	https://dl.acm.org/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notification request to databases for periodical new CIP/CIR relevant publications. • Create records of these new relevant publications from all databases. • Study tri-monthly publication based on developed screening procedure. • Produce a report based
IEEE Xplore Digital Library	A collection of publications, including journals, conference proceedings, and standards.	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/	
Scopus	A collection of large abstracts and citations covering computer science, engineering, and technology and including articles from scholarly journals, conference proceedings, and books.	https://www.scopus.com/home.url	
Science Direct	A collection of full-text articles from various publishers in the fields of science, technology, medicine, including computer science.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/	
Springer Link	A collection of full-text articles and book chapters including journals, conference proceedings	https://link.springer.com/	

Data base name	Description	Access link	EU-CIP activity
	& books in computer science & related fields.		on the screening.
Web of Science	A multidisciplinary citation database that includes articles from scholarly journals,	https://www.webofscience.com/	

Table 2: CIP/CIR Journals

Journal name	Description	Access link	EU-CIP activity
International Journal of Critical Infrastructure Protection	<i>Tri-monthly</i> : Focuses on weaving science, technology, law and policy to craft practical solutions for securing assets in the various critical infrastructure sectors.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-critical-infrastructure-protection	Analyse and study tri-monthly relevant new articles.
International Journal of Information Security	<i>Bi-monthly</i> : Research in information security which offers prompt publication of important technical work, covering system security, network security, content protection, applications.	https://www.springer.com/journal/10207	Analyse and study bi-monthly relevant new articles.
Journal of Infrastructure Preservation and Resilience	<i>Yearly</i> : Collections of articles relating to the discussion of cross-disciplinary and innovative research and engineering practices that preserve the integrity, performance, and resilience of existing infrastructure systems	https://jipr.springeropen.com/	Analyse and study every year relevant new articles.
Journal of Critical Infrastructure Policy	<i>Bi-yearly</i> : Accelerate the improvement of critical infrastructure and community resilience, impact the development of policy and targeted strategies that are capable of addressing the serious challenges facing critical infrastructures on which society depends.	https://www.jcip1.org/	Analyse and study twice a year relevant new articles.
Adversity and Resilience Science:	<i>Quarterly</i> : Focused on protective factors and processes that promote resilience in the face of adversity	https://www.springer.com/journal/42844	Analyse and study quarterly

Journal name	Description	Access link	EU-CIP activity
Journal of Research and Practice	throughout the lifespan. Publishes empirical articles, informed practice reviews, literature reviews, brief reports, book/media reviews, and policy papers.		relevant new articles.

Other relevant information can be gathered from magazines, websites, blogs, and networks and clusters (see Table 3 up to Table 6 below).

Table 3: Magazines

Magazine name	Access link
Australian Infrastructure Magazine	https://infrastructuremagazine.com.au/critical-infrastructure/
Security Magazine	https://www.securitymagazine.com/keywords/7710-critical-infrastructure-security
Cyberprotection Magazine	https://cyberprotection-magazine.com/cybersecurity-challenges-facing-critical-infrastructure
Energy Magazine	https://www.energymagazine.com.au/event/asset-management-for-critical-infrastructure/
Enhancing the resilience of Ireland's critical infrastructure	https://www.eolasmagazine.ie/enhancing-the-resilience-of-irelands-critical-infrastructure/
Mission Critical Magazine Data Centers & Critical Facilities	https://www.missioncriticalmagazine.com/
American Infrastructure Magazine	https://americaninfrastructuremag.com/
Euronews OCEAN Season 5, Episode 5 – Critical infrastructure	https://oceans-and-fisheries.ec.europa.eu/news/euronews-ocean-season-5-episode-5-critical-infrastructure-2023-05-31_en
Risk Management Magazine	https://www.rmmagazine.com/articles/article/2023/03/02/five-cybersecurity-best-practices-for-critical-infrastructure
Deloitte's Global Infrastructure Magazine	https://www2.deloitte.com/au/en/pages/infrastructure-and-capital-projects/articles/deloitte-global-infrastructure-magazine.html

Table 4: Websites

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

Website name	Description	Access link	EU-CIP activity
Cybersecurity & Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) on CIP	Protecting Critical Infrastructure FAQ	https://www.cisa.gov/protecting-critical-infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study periodically these websites based on developed screening procedure. • Produce a report based on the screening.
CISA on CIR	CISA provides guidance to support state, local, and industry partners in identifying critical infrastructure	Critical Infrastructure Security and Resilience	
EU Migration and Home Affairs on Critical infrastructure	Updates on European Critical Infrastructure initiatives, consultation activities, and relevant documents	https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/whats-new/european-critical-infrastructure_en	
Migration and Home Affairs: Critical Infrastructure Warning Information Network (CIWIN)	DG HOME coordinates all activities relating to CIWIN	https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/critical-infrastructure-warning-information-network-ciwin_en	
EU Science Hub: Critical infrastructure protection	EU reference network for CIP/CIR	https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/scientific-activities-z/critical-infrastructure-protection_en	
Bundesministerium des Inneren (English: German Ministry of the Interior) (BMI) on CIP	Information about aims and strategic approach for different CIP/CIR domains (Germany)	https://www.bmi.bund.de/EN/topics/civil-protection/critical-infrastructure-protection/critical-infrastructure-protection-node.html	

Table 5: Blogs

Blog name	Access link
Critical Infrastructure Blogs	https://www.forcepoint.com/blog/tags/critical-infrastructure
The Research ANd Development (RAND) Blog Critical Infrastructure Protection	https://www.rand.org/blog/topic.critical-infrastructure-protection.html
CISCO Blogs on Critical Infrastructure	https://blogs.cisco.com/tag/critical-infrastructure
Unearth's blog	https://www.unearthlabs.com/blog
Omni-Platform Security With Access Technologies (OPSWAT) Critical Infrastructure Protection & Cybersecurity	https://www.opswat.com/blog
Tenable's Securing Critical Infrastructure: It's Complicated	https://www.tenable.com/blog/securing-critical-infrastructure-its-complicated

Table 6: Networks and clusters

Network/Cluster name	Access link
CIPRNET (Critical Infrastructures Preparedness and Resilience Research Network)	https://ciprnet.eu/
ERNICIP (European Reference Network for Critical Infrastructure Protection)	https://ernicip-project.jrc.ec.europa.eu/european-reference-network-critical-infrastructure-protection
ECSCI (European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures)	https://www.finsec-project.eu/ecsci

2.3. Data Collection Process and Data collected (M1-M18)

In this study, the previous survey is extended, and the developed methodology is applied for data collection and analysis. It has to be noted here, that the data curation stage was not completely used. Applying the developed methodology, this study identified two research topics: (i) capability needs and gaps in CIP/CIR, and (ii) technology analysis (risk assessment, threat detection, etc.), a questionnaire data collection modality has been applied, and excel has been used for analysis, extraction and presentation. Using both qualitative and quantitative research methods the following stages of this methodology were used: a) collect raw data based on questionnaires on specific topic, b) analyse collected data, c) extract relevant information and insights, and d) present relevant information and insights. The questionnaire of the survey is designed through a rigorous review of different articles and discussions with the experts from EU-CIP consortium and the ECSCI.

A total of 30 responses from 25 organizations was received where both industry (56.7%), and academia (43.3%) actively participated. Those capability needs were identified (top three from

predefined options), which are more important for CIP/CIR based on the respondents' involvement as shown in Figure 3.

It can be observed from Figure 3 that the specific capability needs with the respective percentile information are as follows: improved detection capabilities (56.7%), training, reskilling and upskilling (43.3%), improved risk and impact assessment capabilities (36.7%), better integration of security tools (36.7%), enhanced adaptability (33.3%), risk prediction and anticipation (33.3%), reduced response times (26.7%), solutions addressing cascading effects (13.3%), transformation of proactive and adaptive protection tools and methods (13.3%), increased transparency (10%), better exploitation of information (10%). Improved detection capabilities, training, reskilling and upskilling are the most selected capability needs from both industry and academia.

Figure 3: Responses on capability needs in the CIP/CIR domain.

In a next step those capability gaps (top three based on pre-defined options) were identified, which are most important for CIP/CIR based on the respondents' involvement as shown in Figure 4. It can be observed from Figure 4 that the specific capability gaps with their respective percentile information are as follows: poor automation (10%), lack of proper control of interconnectedness (13.3%), poor alignment of resilience indicators (13.3%), lack of agreed standards-based stress-testing procedures (13.3%), problems with the classification of Internet of Things (IoT) devices (10%), scalability in the Mitigation of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks (10%), development and deployment of AI-based systems (40%), lack of holistic security management systems (53.3%), gaps in emergency management processes (40%), inability to cope with dynamically evolving threats (56.7%), and poor awareness about modern CIP/CIR challenges (40%). It can be observed that the inability to cope with dynamically evolving threats and the lack of holistic security management systems are the topmost capability gaps.

Figure 4: Responses on capability gaps in the CIP/CIR domain.

Experts were asked to provide inputs for new or emerging cutting-edge technologies that are essential to address the identified gaps in the CIP/CIR domain. It was identified that AI, AI-enabled intrusion detection/prevention, decision support systems using advanced analytics, blockchain technology and 5G networks could provide better bandwidth, speed and reliability for critical infrastructure systems, quantum computing, automation and robotics, among others.

There is still other significant data for how and what information will be fed to the EU-CIP FAIR Observatory based on the inputs from some of the partners of EU-CIP which will be explored in the upcoming roadmaps.

2.4. Analysis Techniques and Analysis Options available so far

Several data analysis techniques and methods are categorised into two main types: 1) qualitative data analysis which extracts data from symbols, texts or words, photos, and observations. and 2) quantitative data analysis which turns raw datasets into numerical data. The top data analysis techniques are shown in Table 7 with their respective techniques and use.

Table 7: Top Data Analysis Techniques to Analyse Data

S. NO.	Title	Description	Techniques	Applicability CIP/CIR
1	Descriptive Statistics	Analysis of a dataset's central tendencies and variability.	Graphical and pictorial methods.	Summarize basic characteristic of data.
2	Inferential Statistics	Predictions or inferences based on a sample of data.	Hypothesis testing, confidence intervals, and regression analysis.	Concluding the data and assessing the significance of findings.

S. NO.	Title	Description	Techniques	Applicability CIP/CIR
3	Regression Analysis	Relationship between one dependent and one or more independent variables.	Linear, logistic, and multiple regression.	Predict and understand causal links.
4	Clustering Analysis	Groups similar data points.	K-means clustering and hierarchical clustering.	Customer segmentation, anomaly detection, pattern recognition.
5	Classification Analysis	Assigns data points to predefined categories or classes.	Decision trees, support vector machines, and neural networks.	Spam email detection, image recognition, and sentiment analysis.
6	Time Series Analysis	Analysis of data over time for forecasting and trend analysis.	Moving averages, autoregressive integrated moving averages (ARIMA), and exponential smoothing.	Show how variables change over time.
7	Text Analysis (Natural Language Processing - NLP)	Extracting insights from textual data.	Sentiment analysis, topic modelling, and named entity recognition.	Analysing customer reviews, social media content, and news articles.
8	Principal Component Analysis	Dimensionality reduction technique, transforming correlated variables into a set of linearly uncorrelated variable.	Unsupervised learning algorithm technique, multivariate statistical technique.	Analyse and visualize high-dimensional data.
9	Anomaly Detection	Identifies unusual patterns or outliers in data.	Statistical methods, clustering-based approaches, and machine learning algorithms.	Fraud detection, network security, and quality control.

S. NO.	Title	Description	Techniques	Applicability CIP/CIR
10	Data Mining	Automated discovery of patterns, associations, and relationships within large datasets.	Association rule mining, frequent pattern analysis, and decision tree mining.	Extract valuable knowledge from data.
11	Machine Learning and Deep Learning	Predictive modelling, classification, and regression tasks.	Random forests, support vector machines, and convolutional neural networks (CNNs), etc.	Solve problems by using explicit programming and based on the layers of neural networks, respectively.
12	Geographic Information Systems (GIS) Analysis	Combines geographical data with spatial analysis techniques.	Computer-based tools to store, visualize, analyse, and interpret geographic data.	Solve location-based problems.

Finally, some future trends for Data Analysis are summarised in Table 8.

Table 8: Top Data Analysis Techniques to Analyse Data

S. NO.	Title	Description	Applicability CIP/CIR
1	Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning Integration, including LLMs (Large Language Models) [1]	automate complex data processing tasks, identify patterns at scale, and make highly accurate predictions	play a central role in data analysis
2	Augmented Analytics	combines AI and NLP to assist data analysts in finding insights. generate narratives, suggest visualizations, and highlight important trends within data	enhance the speed and efficiency of data analysis
3	Data Privacy and Ethical Considerations	privacy concerns and ethical considerations	data handling, transparency, and compliance with regulations like the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

S. NO.	Title	Description	Applicability CIP/CIR
4	Real-time and Streaming Data Analysis	real-time and streaming data analysis for real-time insights	essential for fraud detection, IoT analytics, and monitoring systems
5	Quantum Computing	solving complex problems exponentially	impact on optimization, cryptography, and simulations
6	Edge Analytics	real-time processing and decision-making at the network's edge, reducing latency and bandwidth requirements	Improved real-time and instant decision-making, enhanced security, better scalability, flexibility
7	Explainable AI (XAI)	make AI decisions more understandable, accountable and transparent	improve and debug analytics AI models and increase trust in models' decisions and predictions
8	Data Democratization	democratization of data access and analysis tools	data-driven decisions and efficiencies, enhance data accessibility
9	Advanced Data Visualization	more interactivity, 3D visualization, and Augmented Reality (AR) capabilities	help users explore data in new way
10	Ethnographic Data Analysis	understand human behaviour, cultural dynamics, and social trends	provide a holistic understanding of complex issues
11	Data Analytics Ethics and Bias Mitigation	identify and mitigate bias in algorithms and models	ensuring fair and equitable outcomes

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3. Research and Technological Development

3.1. State-of-the-Art Technologies

The following analysis is based on the detailed study of information and insights from the survey conducted. The technologies and tools that can help close gaps in CIP/CIR will prevent, detect, and mitigate potential threats to Critical Infrastructure (CI), such as cyber-attacks, physical attacks, and natural disasters. The implementation of state-of-the-art technologies and tools can boost the resilience and continuity of CI systems, protecting society from the potentially devastating consequences of their disruption or destruction. From a first round of internal consultation within EU-CIP partners, technologies like cyber-physical threat intelligence, security risk assessment and modelling of cascading effects were perceived as the most promising for mitigating the main encountered capability gaps. The lack of integrated security techniques and the management of cascading consequences are seen as important lacks in CIP/CIR systems. The technology solutions mentioned aim to prevent a range of threats, including cyber-attacks, physical incursions, and natural calamities. The range of tools includes sophisticated cybersecurity technology to protect against cyber-attacks, while physical security technologies improve deterrent and detection. Predictive analytics and machine learning (ML) are becoming powerful tools for detecting vulnerabilities and implementing proactive mitigation strategies. This advanced technology is crucial for strengthening the resilience of CI systems and protecting them from the potentially disastrous effects of being compromised. Integrating these technologies addresses the shortage of holistic security approaches and the comprehensive handling of cascading effects, representative of the current limitations within the CIP/CIR systems.

As result of the first internal survey, the Table 9 shows a core group of state-of-the-art technologies which surfaces as the most pertinent for bridging the gaps in CIP and CIR.

Table 9: State-of-the-art technologies for CIP/CIR (first survey)

State-of-the-art technologies for CIP/CIR (first survey)
Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence
Security Risk Assessment
Impact Assessment Tools
Digital Twins
Anomaly Detection
Cybersecurity Tools
Modelling of Cascading Effects and Interdependencies between CIs
Advances in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning
Unmanned Vehicles and robots
Resilient communication networks
Internet of Things (IoT) Security Solutions
Big Data Analytics
Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) Security
Advanced Encryption Techniques
Integrated Security Platforms / Converged Security Information Management (CSIM)
Physical Security Technologies
Cloud Security Solutions

State-of-the-art technologies for CIP/CIR (first survey)
Collaborative Defence Mechanisms
Chemical, Biological, Radiological, and Nuclear (CBRN) detection, decontamination, and neutralization technologies
Unmanned aerial systems (UAS) or Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) or drones
Counter-UAS / Anti-drone solutions
Adaptive threat hunting
Biometric Authentication
Blockchain/DLT Technology
Closed Circuit Television Systems
Data Loss Prevention Technology
Disinformation Management
End-Point Protection
Image Analysis
Machine Learning – Pattern Detection
Pentesting
Security Information and Event Management
Social Media Analysis
Visual Scene Analysis
Sandboxes
Social Graph Analysis
Surveillance Systems
Malware Detection
Ransomware
5G Communications

A second survey was launched and involving external stakeholders since it is very important to update the findings and to open the survey to gather external input. The results obtained (see Table 10) show that in the dynamic realm of CIP and CIR, it is crucial to possess a thorough comprehension of and effectively integrate cutting-edge technologies to address the identified capability gaps. Consider that some technologies were mentioned again in the second survey due to their importance.

Table 10: Identified state-of-the-art technologies from second survey

State-of-the-art technologies for CIP/CIR (second survey)
Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence
Security Risk Assessment (dynamic risk assessment)
Impact assessment Tools (safety and security assessment models, adaptive and anticipatory models)
Digital Twins
Anomaly Detection
Cybersecurity Tools
Modelling of cascading effects and interdependencies between CIs
Artificial Intelligence, Generative Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning
Detection and Prevention Systems

State-of-the-art technologies for CIP/CIR (second survey)
Decision Support Systems
Blockchain technology
Quantum Computing
5G network
Automation and Robotics (autonomous drones and robotics for surveillance)
Predictive Analytics
Biometric Authentication
Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)
Edge Computing

Some advanced technologies identified with the second survey are summarised and elaborated below.

- **AI** stands at the forefront, offering predictive and preventive capabilities in cybersecurity, physical security, and the optimization of resource management. Its general applicability allows for the discovery of non-obvious threat patterns, enabling rapid crisis responses through real-time data analysis. AI's role is further extended in the field of **ML**, where increased automation and advanced analytics contribute to environmental protection and sustainability.
- Powered by AI and **decision support systems (DSS)**, **detection and prevention systems** efficiently manage cyber threat intelligence by utilising high-performance computation (HPC). The aforementioned collaboration improves the precision and velocity of cyber threat detection and analysis, thereby enabling a proactive stance towards security.
- **Blockchain** technology serves as a crucial facilitator, providing a framework for decentralised data administration that fortifies the resilience and security of critical infrastructures. When combined with **quantum computing**, this technology establishes a resilient defence mechanism against cyber threats by implementing threat detection processes more quickly and providing quantum-resistant cryptography for data protection.
- **5G networks** provide significant improvements in capacity, speed, and reliability, which are crucial for reducing reaction times during emergencies. Similarly, using **robotics** and **automation** in maintaining and repairing essential infrastructures enhances resilience by decreasing reaction times.
- **Predictive analytics** utilises ML and data analytics to identify possible weaknesses and dangers, allowing for preventive actions to be implemented. **Biometric authentication** enhances physical security measures by ensuring secure access to important places.
- **Quantum computing** not only offers advanced cybersecurity solutions but also promises secure communication channels through quantum cryptography, revolutionizing the way we protect and manage critical infrastructures.
- **Trusted execution environments** and **generative AI models** represent the cutting edge in advanced threat detection. These technologies enable the generation and analysis of data across various formats, providing dynamic support in decision-making processes.
- Incorporating **digital twins**, **cyber-physical threat intelligence**, and **security risk assessment** tools into the CIP/CIR framework allows for a nuanced understanding of potential disruptions and the cascading effects of cyber-physical threats. These methods, along with **cybersecurity tools** and **modelling of cascading effects**, form a comprehensive strategy for safeguarding critical infrastructures.

- Emerging technologies such as **blockchain for supply chain integrity, autonomous drones and robotics for surveillance, and edge computing for fast data processing**, further augment the resilience and security of critical infrastructure systems. These innovations, alongside **dynamic risk assessment, safety and security assessment models**, and **adaptive and anticipatory models**, ensure a robust framework for critical infrastructure protection and resilience.

To improve CIP/CIR in Europe, the research and technological development roadmap requires a comprehensive strategy. This entails not only further integration of these cutting-edge technologies, but also a comprehensive understanding of their interrelationships and possible vulnerabilities. By maintaining a harmonious equilibrium between investment in protection measures, disaster recovery tactics, and routine system updates, it is possible to establish an infrastructure that is not only robust and resilient against actual threats but also able to withstand novel challenges and threats.

The aggregated view of state-of-the-art technologies for CIP/CIR underscores the imperative for a coherent and adaptive strategy. It calls for an integration of advanced technological enablers, from AI and quantum computing to blockchain and predictive analytics, tailored to meet the evolving demands of critical infrastructure protection. Through a collaborative effort among stakeholders, these technologies can significantly contribute to bridging the identified capability gaps, fostering a secure, resilient, and sustainable critical infrastructure landscape in line with the EU-CIP vision.

In order to achieve a comprehensive and holistic overview of the technological landscape for closing the pertinent gaps found in CIP/CIR, the results of the two surveys were revisited and grouped into broader macro-categories that reflect their primary application areas or underlying technological principles. The condensed version organised into macro-categories, with specific technologies mentioned under each category is shown in Table 11.

This reorganisation supports understanding of the broad technological domains and the specific innovations or tools that fall under each category. It eases comprehension of the overall landscape of emerging security technologies.

Table 11: Candidate technologies to close gaps in CIP/CIR arranged in macro-categories

- **Cybersecurity and Threat Intelligence:**
 - Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence
 - Security Risk Assessment (dynamic risk assessment)
 - Cybersecurity Tools
 - AI, Generative AI, and ML for cybersecurity
 - IoT Security Solutions
 - Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) Security
 - Cloud Security Solutions
 - Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) (Advanced Encryption Techniques, Blockchain technology)
- **Digital Modelling and Simulation:**
 - Impact Assessment Tools (safety and security assessment models, adaptive and anticipatory models)
 - Digital Twins
 - Modelling of cascading effects and interdependencies between Critical Infrastructures (CIs)
- **Detection and Monitoring Technologies:**
 - Anomaly Detection
 - Integrated Security Platforms / Converged Security Information Management (CSIM) (detection, prevention, decision support, predictive analytics)
 - Collaborative Defence Mechanisms
 - CBRN detection, decontamination, and neutralization technologies
 - Counter-UAS / Anti-drone solutions
- **Advanced Computing and Data Analytics:**
 - Enhanced computing technologies (Quantum Computing, Edge Computing, Big Data Analytics)
 - Automation and Robotics (unmanned and/or autonomous drones/vehicles and robotics for surveillance)
- **Network and Communication Security:**
 - Resilient communication networks (Ten Gigabit (XG) network)
- **Physical Security and Access Control:**
 - Physical Security Technologies (Biometric Authentication)

3.1.1. Technological future trends and advancements in CIP/CIR domain

Within the next five years, the CIP/CIR sector will be profoundly impacted by emerging trends and significant developments. **ML and AI** technologies represent the major trend. These technologies will improve threat detection and response capabilities and help create reliable implementations. As climate change induces more disruptive events and urban populations demand high-technology services, AI and ML will be crucial for connecting systems in critical infrastructure and enhancing resilience against digital and physical threats.

The integration of AI and ML with **IoT** and **Edge computing** technologies is anticipated to revolutionize real-time monitoring and quick response mechanisms in critical infrastructure systems.

The collaboration between **advanced robotics** and the expansion of **5G networks** will enable the provision of requisite data transmission speed, capacity, and dependability, thereby guaranteeing improved emergency communication and coordination. The utilisation of **blockchain technology** is anticipated to strengthen its position in strengthening the resilience and security of critical infrastructure by means of decentralised and secure data management systems. This will be crucial in ensuring data integrity and enhancing trust in digital transactions and information sharing within CIR.

Additionally, the emergence of **quantum computing** and **post-quantum cryptography** appears on the horizon addressing the paramount need for secure communication channels and encryption methods capable of withstanding quantum-era threats. This advancement will be essential in safeguarding critical data and maintaining the integrity of vital communication networks against emerging cyber threats.

Digital Twins (DT) and **Data Spaces (DS)** technologies will offer additional unprecedented capabilities in simulating and analysing complex cyber-physical systems. These technologies will enable effective implementation of **Human In the Loop (HIL)** approaches, significantly reducing the effort needed for building and testing critical infrastructure systems while ensuring policy-compliant use of sensitive data.

Furthermore, the sector is expected to witness a shift towards **hyper-automation integrated with AI**, streamlining the CIP cycle from monitoring to recovery, and enhancing the automation and management of critical infrastructure systems. This integration promises to deliver **real-time analysis, predictive modelling, and autonomous decision-making**, thus significantly improving operational efficiency and resilience.

The onset of **Sixth generation technology standard for wireless communications (6G)** and **advanced cyber-physical systems** will further empower the CIP/CIR domain, offering enhanced communication capabilities and supporting more effective data sharing and coordination among CI entities. This will significantly contribute to expediting incident response times and enhancing service provision in a comprehensive manner.

By addressing the highlighted shortcomings in capabilities, these advancements will improve the overall resilience, efficiency, and security of the critical infrastructure system. Critical infrastructure systems will be more prepared to handle a wide variety of emerging risks and problems by using advanced detection capabilities, expanded risk assessment tools, and greater operational flexibility. The CIP/CIR sector will make significant progress in aligning with the EU CIP target and improving the security and resilience of infrastructure across Europe due to upcoming trends and improvements.

3.2. General benefits of new technologies

New technologies integrated into critical sectors provide advantages that improve efficiency, security, and resilience in critical infrastructure systems. The developments are driven by the goal of enhancing operational efficiency to offer services more efficiently and minimise downtime. This is accomplished by automating processes and optimising supply chains, resulting in enhanced service delivery, reduced costs, and decreased waste, leading to a more efficient and resilient operating structure. Integrating new technologies might potentially save costs by decreasing operating and maintenance expenses, improving system dependability, and reducing downtime for critical components.

Enhanced monitoring and analysis, using specific cybersecurity protocols at the same time, can improve the protection of critical infrastructures against emerging cyber threats. Improving security measures is crucial not only for mitigating the probability of incidents and intrusions but also for preserving the reliability of critical services. The implementation of predictive analytics and artificial intelligence additionally supports threat detection and management by enabling the timely and accurate identification of potential threats. Sophisticated systems and procedures strengthen essential infrastructures to prevent significant breaches and disastrous incidents, guaranteeing uninterrupted operation and preventing service disruptions. The resilience can be strengthened by using digital twins and advanced modelling tools to simulate and analyse probable disruptions, thereby enhancing readiness and reaction plans.

The strategic integration of advanced technologies has the potential to significantly elevate operational efficiency, bolster security measures, and fortify resilience, alongside enhancing decision-making processes. This underscores the importance of a targeted approach in technology adoption, ensuring that investments are aligned with the objectives of improving resilience, security, and operational efficiency. Utilising and evaluating e.g. extensive data from several sources enable a more informed and data-driven decision-making strategy. Possessing this knowledge is essential for efficient risk management, as it empowers critical infrastructures to predict, adjust to, and alleviate potential hazards with greater precision.

Furthermore, the adoption of novel technologies likely fosters innovation and provides a competitive advantage. It enables critical industries to address a broad range of hazards, including ones that were previously unknown, thereby enhancing their ability to respond and be prepared. Adaptability is crucial for dealing with changing attack vectors and making use of new methods for protection and resilience.

The environmental consequences of using new technology must not be ignored. Clean energy innovations and sustainable practices can make operations more environmentally friendly by decreasing the carbon footprint of essential infrastructures. This dedication to environmental sustainability not only aids worldwide initiatives to address climate change but also guarantees that essential industries continue to be sustainable and responsible managers of the resources they use.

New technologies in vital industries provide several advantages, including increased efficiency and production, greater security, higher resilience, and better risk management. The innovations can help to safeguard and optimise critical infrastructure comprehensively for meeting current and future needs. This is fully aligned with the EU-CIP objective for enhancing Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience in Europe.

The general benefits of new technologies can be briefly summarised as 1) quick access to information, facilitated learning, 2) breaking the distance barrier, simplifying tasks, providing entertainment, 3) increased productivity and efficiency, 4) increased life expectancy, and creating new jobs.

The benefits of new technologies as per collected data are increase in efficiency, improved/more precise and faster response, identifying potential risks, increase awareness and prevention capabilities, enhancing safety, cost reduction, improved operational efficiency, enhanced security measures, real-time monitoring and analytics, improve predictive maintenance, enhanced efficiency and productivity, improved decision-making, improved risk management, enable innovation and competitive capabilities, support in improving decision-making, automation of actions and monitoring, early warning and risk information exchange.

3.3. Key adoption and implementation challenges

Adopting state-of-the-art technologies in CIP/CIR domains presents a series of complex challenges and barriers, such as:

- **Technical and integration challenges:** Connection to legacy systems is a paramount issue. Critical infrastructures often rely on dated systems that do not easily integrate with newer technologies. This creates a barrier to seamless operation, raising concerns over data exchange, system compatibility, and heightened cybersecurity vulnerabilities. The complex nature of integrating new technology with current systems can lead to increased costs and delays, necessitating a careful balance between upgrading and maintaining operational continuity.
- **Organizational and awareness challenges:** The challenge of CI operators understanding which game-changing technology is available or may be adaptable underscores the need for enhanced knowledge sharing and breaking down silos between different CI types and expertise areas. Similarly, the lack of management acknowledgment and awareness can obstacle the adoption of necessary advancements. This situation is compounded by the need for certification of cybersecurity solutions, where amendments to design are not always feasible in already certified systems. This is limiting the incorporation of cutting-edge security measures.
- **Regulatory and compliance constraints:** The adoption of innovative technologies is further complicated by regulatory challenges. Complex regulatory regimes can delay or deter the implementation of new solutions, particularly when certification processes do not accommodate updates or integrations of advanced cybersecurity technologies. The balancing act of ensuring data privacy and adherence to regulations like GDPR while harnessing the power of large data sets for analytics and decision-making represents a critical compliance challenge.
- **Financial barriers:** The prohibitive cost associated with implementing state-of-the-art technology often prevents numerous organisations from doing so. This matter assumes particular significance for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), given that they might confront challenges in distributing the necessary financial capital towards investments in emerging technologies. Time constraints, financial restrictions, and a lack of qualified personnel are all instances of resource limitations that have the potential to significantly impede the adoption of new technologies.
- **Cybersecurity and privacy concerns** arise from the unintended expansion of the attack surface that can result from the adoption of new technologies. Constant difficulty exists in ensuring that data privacy is managed in accordance with regulatory requirements while safeguarding against novel threats with robust cybersecurity measures.
- **Supply chain security:** Risks such as manipulation and counterfeiting are introduced by the complexity of global supply chains. Stringent verification procedures are required to safeguard the supply chain for critical infrastructure components against the intrusion of compromised devices. The concerns mentioned are addressed under the Directive on security of network and information systems (NIS-2), and its effective implementation can significantly reduce these challenges. In particular, NIS-2 directive underlines the importance of comprehensive risk management approaches and the application of security measures.
- **Cultural and skills gap:** For organisations to successfully incorporate new technologies, it is vital to overcome resistance to change and close the skills gap. Constant obstacles consist of

e.g. fostering an organization-wide environment that encourages innovation and providing adequate training for staff to effectively manage and oversee modern technology.

In order to effectively address these challenges, it is crucial to implement a comprehensive approach that incorporates various elements, including stakeholder collaboration, regulatory flexibility, strategic investments, comprehensive training initiatives, and robust cybersecurity measures. In accordance with the EU-CIP vision, the complete capabilities of cutting-edge technologies to strengthen the security and robustness of Europe's vital infrastructure can solely be realised by overcoming these challenges.

3.3.1. Recommendations to improve the integration and utilisation of advanced technologies

Implementing a comprehensive plan that includes all critical components which could be affected by a threat is advised to improve integration and utilisation of new technologies in CIP/CIR.

It is crucial to create a **trust framework** to facilitate the safe exchange of information across parties. This, in turn, is vital for ensuring a timely and effective response to threats. Encouraging the use of **serious gaming** and convening stakeholders at both formal and informal meetings will bridge gaps between different CI domains, fostering a culture of collaboration and reducing operational silos.

Adopting a “**Secure by Design**” **philosophy** is paramount, ensuring that security measures are embedded within the certification processes of new technologies. This proactive approach guarantees that security is not an afterthought but a foundational component of technological development. Additionally, the creation of precise **rules and procedures for technology integration** into CI systems will alleviate uncertainties, promoting a smooth adoption process.

Promoting **stakeholder cooperation** is vital. This involves not just CI operators and policymakers but extends to regulators and technology suppliers, ensuring a harmonized approach towards technological advancements. Equally, enhancing **funding for R&D** in critical areas such as cybersecurity, AI, and robotics will pave the way for innovative solutions tailored to the unique challenges of the CIP/CIR sector.

To cultivate an environment of **continuous improvement and adaptation**, encouraging a **culture that values creativity and experimentation** is recommended. This includes the execution of pilot projects to gauge the effectiveness and impacts of new technologies before widespread deployment. Organizing **regular training and awareness initiatives** ensures that staff managing critical infrastructures are well-versed in the latest technological advancements, enabling seamless integration and utilization.

Moreover, leveraging **public-private partnerships** could significantly facilitate technology transfer and knowledge sharing, essential for the dynamic landscape of CIP/CIR. Creative financing mechanisms should be explored to stimulate private sector investment in technological advancements, thereby fostering an ecosystem of innovation and collaboration.

By implementing these recommendations, derived directly from the insights of operators, policymakers, and industry experts, the integration and utilization of state-of-the-art technologies in the CIP/CIR domain can be markedly improved. These measures not only address the immediate challenges of technology adoption but also lay a robust foundation for the sustainable enhancement of critical infrastructure resilience and protection, in line with the overarching EU-CIP vision.

3.4. Supporting R&I activities

As described in the previous sections, technologies for CIP and CIR exist and therefore there is the need to overcome the challenges for their uptake as well as to keep improving them in view of the dynamic changes of the threats landscape, as well as to address the interoperability across available solutions.

In this sense the proposed R&I activities to develop technological enablers for improving CIP/CIR are:

1. Data management and integration:

Across critical infrastructure sectors, obtaining high-quality, comprehensive data is essential for AI-driven threat detection and prediction systems. Challenges such as limited sensor coverage, data silos, and variability in data formats need to be addressed to ensure effective threat foresight. This calls for the need of integrating disparate data sources into coherent systems, requiring efforts to ensure data quality, consistency, and interoperability across critical infrastructure sectors. Achieving interoperability between different digital systems and technologies is necessary for seamless communication within and across critical infrastructure sectors, highlighting the importance of standardized protocols and interfaces.

2. Complexity of dynamic and evolving threat landscape:

Critical infrastructure faces diverse threats, including natural disasters, terrorist attacks, cyber breaches, and infrastructure failures. Developing sophisticated AI algorithms capable of analysing and predicting such a complex threat landscape requires multidisciplinary expertise and advanced modelling techniques. Further, the threats to critical infrastructure are constantly evolving, demanding adaptive and responsive threat detection capabilities. AI algorithms must continuously learn from new data and adapt to emerging threats in real-time, posing significant technical challenges in developing agile systems.

3. Training framework development:

Ensuring the workforce of critical infrastructure is equipped with essential skills in data analytics, cybersecurity, and software programming is crucial for effectively adopting and operating digital technologies across critical infrastructure sectors. This requires the development of a harmonized training framework for the different profiles of users within the sector. There is also the need for training approaches devoted to regional response capacities in disaster management, encompassing standardized training modules, lessons learned repositories, and guidelines for practitioner organizations. Moreover, additional research is needed to promote education on disaster risk reduction, engaging citizens through tailored educational content and distribution methods suited to various audiences.

4. Public acceptance and trust:

Building public trust and acceptance of digital technologies in critical infrastructure is crucial, necessitating transparency and assurance regarding privacy, data security, and reliability.

5. Interdisciplinary collaboration:

Effective threat foresight requires collaboration between experts in various fields, including engineering, cybersecurity, data science, social science and risk analysis. Bridging disciplinary gaps and integrating insights into AI-driven systems is vital for holistic risk assessment and mitigation strategies.

6. Collaboration enhancement across projects on CIP/CIR:

Research is needed to develop frameworks and tools for enhancing collaboration between projects within the CIP/CIR thematic areas. This could involve the development of platforms or methodologies to facilitate collaboration, particularly in areas of common interest such as citizen involvement, data management, and communication.

Further research could focus on terminology standardization to ensure clear communication and avoid duplication of work, potentially involving the development of standardized terminology and guidelines.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

4. Framework for Development of new Technologies, Techniques, Methods and Tools contributing to fill the identified Capability Gaps

4.1. Regulatory Framework

The regulatory framework for this roadmap is given primarily by the EU Directives Critical Entities Resilience (CER) and NIS2. Further work in the project will establish needs for additional supporting documents, both at the EU and national levels.

4.2. Standardisation Framework

The main calling of the relevant standards is to provide guidance on developing new technologies, techniques, methods and tools, as well as the competencies and business models to create relevant and realistic recommendations in an increasingly challenging world of CIP/CIR. The standardisation in the area of new technologies for enhancing resilience of CIP/CIR and filling the gaps identified, has the following main levels:

- The international standards (e.g. ISO, IEC – e.g. ISO 31000 series and 223xx series).
- EU standards (e.g. CEN, EN).
- National standards (e.g. DIN, AFNOR, BSI...).
- Industry standards (e.g. API, ASME, ...).
- Company standards.

In real case applications, i.e. in operation of CIs, the standards of each level are applied within a network, either at one single level or, more often, combining the levels. An example of such a network in the area of risk and resilience, at the level of ISO is shown in Figure 5.

The EU-CIP project, within its FAIR Observatory, allows to represent the network dynamically, based directly on the information about the standards stored in the database (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Schematic representation of the risk and resilience standards network at level of ISO standards.

EU-CIP FAIR Data Observatory **EU-YRI**

Adaptation to climate change - Guidelines on vulnerability, impacts and risk assessment

Reference name: ISO 14091:2021

Description: Scope: This document gives guidelines for assessing the risks related to the potential impacts of climate change. It describes how to understand vulnerability and how to develop and implement a sound risk assessment in the context of climate change. It can be used for assessing both present and future climate change risks. Risk assessment according to this document provides a basis for climate change adaptation planning, implementation, and monitoring and evaluation for any organization, regardless of size, type and nature. Stage: published

Document(s): ISO 14091:2021 (01.01.2021)

Figure 6: Representation of the risk and resilience standards network at level of ISO standards created with support of the EU-CIP FAIR Observatory (here: the automatically and dynamically created network of standards related to the topic “Adaptation to climate change”).

The CIP/CIR standardization framework should support all activities, including decision making across all levels of the organisation. It should support governance, strategy and technical and management, and ensure consistency and the effectiveness across all areas of the organization. It should include strategy and planning, organizational resilience, Information Technology (IT), corporate governance, human resources, compliance, quality, health and safety, business continuity, crisis management and security. In the ISO standardization environment, it is supported by the methodologies listed in IEC/ISO 31010 Risk Management – Risk assessment techniques, providing guidance on the selection and application of techniques for assessing risk and resilience in a wide range of situations. With the new ISO Technical Specification (TS) 31050:2023, dealing with managing emerging risks for enhanced resilience, the decision makers will be better equipped to manage both known (ISO 31000) and emerging risks (ISO TS 31050). To this aim, ISO 31050 delivers structured context (e.g. definitions, drivers, metrics, etc.), emerging risk management framework, the

procedure, the guidance for common format(s) for interoperability and indicators. It provides application examples in its informative annexes and facilitates best practices, enhancing resilience, promoting agility, assisting transformation, delivering insight and foresight, and integrating resources – all for enhancing resilience of critical infrastructures. The standard is monitored by the ISO Technical Committees TC262 and TC292.

4.3. Qualification framework for new Technologies, Techniques, Methods and Tools

The qualification framework and the qualification process for new technologies, techniques, methods and tools contributing to fill the identified capability CIP/CIP-related gaps should comprise the following main activities:

- Establishing an overall plan for the qualification.
- Establishing a qualification basis including requirements, specifications and descriptions, and defining the limiting parameters for the new solutions.
- Screening the solutions (e.g. the technology) based on the degree of newness to focus the effort where the related uncertainty is most significant.
- Planning and executing comprehensive and representative data collection.
- Analysing and, when and where appropriate, re-specification of functional and other requirements of the new solution(s).

4.4. Governance

All the above frameworks for the development of new technologies, techniques, methods and tools contributing to fill the identified CIP/CIR capability gaps should, at the end of the development, fit the governance (social/societal and ethical) framework shown in Figure 7. The framework shows that as the complexity, uncertainty and ambiguity of a resilience CI issue and of the solutions, increase (from simple ones to complex, uncertain and ambiguous ones), the stakeholders' participation should increase, too. For the most complex cases, it would imply that the good governance and acceptability of the new solutions/technologies/tools can be ensured only by means of through participation of all the stakeholders – including, for the most complex cases the society as a whole.

5. Training and skills development

The EU-CIP training and skills development roadmap was introduced in the previous report (v2) and is structured around four key pillars. The following paragraphs provide an expanded explanation of these pillars, offering additional details beyond those presented earlier:

1. **Skills Gap Analysis, Skills Profiles Identification, and Learning Paths (2022-2024):**

This is a first step of the roadmap that has been carried out by the EU-CIP project as part of its training activities. The project has produced a catalogue of 140+ (existing) CIP/CIR related courses, while it has also identified training as one of the main capability needs/gaps expressed by CI operators and CIP/CIR vendors. Several of the identified gaps are cybersecurity related, while the need for training and upskilling CI employees in emerging technologies is also expressed. EU-CIP has specified the skills profiles that will be required to support the envisaged CIP/CIR improvements. An initial set of profiles identified by the EU-CIP project, along with the main individual skills that they comprise include:

- **Cybersecurity Specialist**
 - Proficiency in identifying and mitigating cyber threats.
 - Knowledge of encryption methods and security protocols.
 - Ability to conduct vulnerability assessments and penetration testing.
 - Familiarity with incident response procedures and forensic analysis.
- **Risk Management Analyst**
 - Expertise in assessing risks to critical infrastructure.
 - Ability to develop risk management strategies and plans.
 - Proficiency in analysing data to identify potential vulnerabilities.
 - Strong communication skills to convey risk information effectively.
- **Emergency Response Coordinator**
 - Experience in coordinating response efforts during emergencies.
 - Knowledge of emergency management protocols and procedures.
 - Ability to communicate effectively with internal and external stakeholders during crisis situations.
 - Familiarity with incident command systems and emergency communication systems.
- **Physical Security Specialist**
 - Proficiency in designing and implementing physical security measures.
 - Knowledge of access control systems and surveillance technologies.
 - Experience in conducting security assessments and audits.
 - Ability to develop security policies and procedures.
- **Network Infrastructure Engineer**
 - Expertise in designing and maintaining network infrastructure.
 - Knowledge of network protocols and technologies.
 - Ability to troubleshoot network issues and optimize performance.
 - Familiarity with network security principles and best practices.
- **Critical Infrastructure Resilience Planner**
 - Experience in developing resilience plans for critical infrastructure.
 - Knowledge of resilience frameworks and methodologies.
 - Ability to conduct risk assessments and prioritize mitigation efforts.
 - Strong analytical and problem-solving skills.
- **Incident Response Manager**

- Proficiency in managing incident response teams.
- Experience in developing and implementing incident response plans.
- Knowledge of forensic analysis techniques and evidence preservation.
- Ability to coordinate with law enforcement and regulatory agencies during investigations.
- **Compliance Auditor**
 - Expertise in auditing critical infrastructure for compliance with regulations and standards.
 - Knowledge of relevant regulatory frameworks and industry guidelines.
 - Ability to conduct compliance assessments and identify gaps.
 - Strong attention to detail and analytical skills.
- **Industrial Control Systems (ICS) Engineer**
 - Experience in designing and maintaining industrial control systems.
 - Knowledge of Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems and protocols.
 - Ability to assess and mitigate cyber threats targeting ICS.
 - Familiarity with industry-specific regulations and best practices.
- **Crisis Communication Specialist**
 - Proficiency in developing and implementing crisis communication plans.
 - Experience in managing communication channels during emergencies.
 - Ability to craft clear and concise messages for internal and external stakeholders.
 - Familiarity with media relations and public speaking.
- **Business Continuity Planner**
 - Expertise in developing business continuity plans for critical infrastructure.
 - Knowledge of continuity planning frameworks and methodologies.
 - Ability to identify and prioritize critical business functions.
 - Experience in conducting continuity exercises and simulations.
- **Data Privacy Officer**
 - Proficiency in ensuring compliance with data privacy regulations.
 - Knowledge of data protection laws and standards.
 - Ability to assess data privacy risks and develop mitigation strategies.
 - Experience in managing data breach incidents and conducting investigations.
- **Physical Infrastructure Engineer**
 - Experience in designing and maintaining physical infrastructure for critical facilities.
 - Knowledge of building codes and construction standards.
 - Ability to assess structural vulnerabilities and recommend improvements.
 - Familiarity with disaster-resistant building techniques and technologies.
- **Supply Chain Security Manager**
 - Expertise in securing supply chains for critical infrastructure.
 - Knowledge of supply chain risk management principles.
 - Ability to assess supplier security practices and enforce compliance.
 - Experience in developing contingency plans for supply chain disruptions.
- **Cyber Threat Intelligence Analyst**
 - Proficiency in collecting and analysing cyber threat intelligence.
 - Knowledge of threat actors and their tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTPs).
 - Ability to produce actionable intelligence reports for decision-makers.
 - Experience in threat hunting and proactive threat mitigation strategies.

In the scope of EU-CIP, a learning path for each skill profile is created. Both the learning paths and training catalogue are part of the Learning Activities in EU-CIP. It's essential to recognize that the learning paths proposed by the EU-CIP represent just a starting point and further extensive resources will be necessary to fully accomplish the scope of the roadmap.

2. **Training Resources Development (2023-2026):** This phase of the roadmap will deal with the development of the required learning resources to support skills development in areas and ways that cover the identified gaps. EU-CIP has already started developing training programmes, courses, webinars, among other actions. Training organizations, education providers, and the human resources departments of CI operators and CIP/CIR solutions vendors will be mobilized and incentivized in this process. EU-CIP is already contributing to the development of training resources, aiming to provide examples of the type of resources needed and of their role in the upskilling process. Such resources include the following courses that are accessible through the project's YouTube Channel [2] and Knowledge Hub [3]:

- A **tutorial course** that aims at introducing **Video Surveillance Systems for Physical Security** in CI. The course can be found on EU-CIP YouTube channel.
- A **tutorial course** that aims at introducing **Artificial Intelligence and its use cases** in CIP. The course can be found on EU-CIP YouTube channel
- A **training catalogue** that provides a single-entry point to **CIP related training resources**, notably resources from third-party providers.

Acknowledging this, EU-CIP is also providing a catalogue of third-party training courses/resources that can help professionals in their CIP/CIR upskilling and reskilling efforts.

3. **Training Delivery – Reskilling and Upskilling Programs Delivery (2024-2027):** This phase of the roadmap shall emphasise the delivery of the programmes and other resources developed towards realizing the upskilling and reskilling processes required for the future of CIP/CIR. The delivery shall be planned in-line with the set goals in the first version of the roadmap (e.g. towards reskilling a specific amount of CI professionals at the EU level). Policy makers must develop policies (e.g. incentives, training programmes, awareness raising programmes, funding programmes) that support the delivery of the required reskilling and upskilling programs. CI operators and CIP/CIR solutions vendors/integrators shall be supported in their engagement in the upskilling and reskilling processes as part of their human capital development strategies. They must adopt an efficient training roadmap to ensure reskilling and upskilling benefits both their companies and employees. This part of the roadmap should:

- Foster a continuous learning environment, offering these learning paths and resources to employees to enhance their skills for career advancement.
- Promote cross-functional training to expand skill sets and adaptability, and establish mentorship and coaching programs for knowledge sharing and soft skill development.
- Encourage obtaining industry-recognized certifications, and regularly assess and adapt reskilling efforts based on feedback and performance metrics.
- Collaborate with EU-CIP, other project as well as educational institutions for specialized training to secure support for reskilling initiatives.
- Stay adaptable to changes, ensure reskilling is inclusive, maintain open communication about reskilling programs, and regularly evaluate the return on investment of reskilling in terms of employee retention, innovation, and productivity.
- Ensure that all reskilling and upskilling activities comply with regional, national and EU policies and regulations related to workforce training and development.

4. **Progress Tracking – Adjustments – Fine Tuning (2027-2030):** A fine tuning process shall be implemented as part of this step of the roadmap. It entails the tracking of the upskilling/reskilling progress and its assessment against the set goals at organizational, regional, national and EU levels. Moreover, stakeholders' feedback must be obtained. Stakeholders feedback and the outcomes of the assessment will be used accordingly to adjust and fine tune the educational, training and upskilling processes. The fine-tuning may lead to the development or adjustment of training resources, the structuring of additional training programs, as well as to actions for improving engagement and delivery.

6. Research and Technological Development Action Plan for filling the Gaps

The EU-CIP project recommends a set of actions aimed at developing necessary technologies, complemented by targeted policy measures. These actions were already presented in the initial list of implementation actions provided in v2 (Annex E.1, cf. Figure 8) and are summarised and enhanced below. Moreover, they will be further detailed in the forthcoming EU-CIP roadmap documents (v4-v6). Additionally, EU-CIP proposes best practices for monitoring and evaluating the roadmap's implementation based on the suggested actions.

Figure 8: The Three Parts of the Roadmap.

6.1. Research and Technological Development Actions

The research and technology roadmap includes the following actions and steps/phases (cf. Figure 9):

Step/Phase 1: Needs, Gaps and Market Analysis (2022-2024):

- Action 1.1:** Specification of Capability Gaps and Needs. Roadmap v1, v2 and the present v3 are steps towards this direction.
- Action 1.2:** Analysis of Market Trends and Dynamics.
- Action 1.3:** Analysis of Technologies that can fill-in the gaps, as performed earlier in this document, including analysis of standards and applicable regulations.
- Action 1.4:** Mapping of state-of-the-art technologies and standards to the various gaps i.e. association of technologies to capability needs and gaps.

Step/Phase 2: Research Activities to address the Capability Gaps (2021-2025):

- Action 2.1:** Specification of technologies and standards that are required to address existing gaps, with emphasis on technologies that go beyond the state of the art and on standards that go beyond the state of practice.
- Action 2.2:** Incorporation of the beyond state-of-the-art technologies and standards in corporate and governmental research roadmaps.

3. **Action 2.3:** Design of research and innovation programs, including programs by funding agencies.
4. **Action 2.4:** Specification of incentives and policies for engaging CIs operators and other stakeholders in research and innovation development activities.
5. **Action 2.5:** Support for technological development activities linked to standards.

Step/Phase 3: Development and Field Validation of Innovative Technological Solutions (2022-2026)

1. **Action 3.1:** Establishment of experimentation infrastructures (e.g. testbeds, sandboxes, labs) to facilitate the validation of technologies.
2. **Action 3.2:** Incentivizing and strengthening Synergies between testing and validating infrastructures (e.g. Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs), Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs)) and CI Operators.
3. **Action 3.3:** Integration of research results into innovative technological solutions that will be deployed and validated in pilot sites and on the field (Technical Readiness Level (TRL) ≥ 5 and $TRL \leq 8$).
4. **Action 3.4:** Planning and implementation of testing and experimentation projects, programs and related co-funded activities.
5. **Action 3.5:** Creation of programs that support innovation and validation activities, including research collaborations, co-creation, and synergetic development of standards.

Step/Phase 4: R&I on CIP Integration and Collaboration Activities (Regional, National, EU Levels) (2022-2026)

1. **Action 4.1:** Regional and National collaboration for R&I activities on CIP/CIR including funding programs.
2. **Action 4.2:** International collaboration for R&I activities on CIP/CIR solutions, including funding programs and cross-border activities.
3. **Action 4.3:** Planning of technology integration and interoperability initiatives for secure and resilient value chains, as well as for resilient interconnected infrastructures.
4. **Action 4.4:** Public private partnerships for value chain resilience and supply chain resilience.
5. **Action 4.5:** Clustering and collaboration for sharing of knowledge and best practices at EU-level.

Step/Phase 5: Commercialization of Innovative Solutions and Deployment in Production (2025-2028)

1. **Action 5.1:** Access to finance measures towards exploitation and commercialization. The EU-CIP Open Call Type B provides an example in this direction, yet a much larger scale is required.
2. **Action 5.2:** Links to innovation support structures (e.g. security incubators, DIHs) for mentoring and support in Intellectual Property (IP) and other commercialization issues.
3. **Action 5.3:** Structures and programs to facilitate technology solution adoption in EU markets, including market access plans.
4. **Action 5.4:** Standards compliance and adoption auditing, towards increasing the standards-based adherence of the solutions, while providing feedback to SDOs.

Step/Phase 6: Monitoring and Continuous Improvement (2027-2030)

1. **Action 6.1:** Establishment of channels (e.g. forums, consultations, coordination and support actions) towards continuous collection of Stakeholders' feedbacks.
2. **Action 6.2:** Regular monitoring of technology evolution, including monitoring of the research and scientific state of the art in CIP/CIR related topics.
3. **Action 6.3:** Refinement of policy measures, including funding programs and related R&I policies. This will be based on integration of stakeholders' feedback and information about technology evolution.
4. **Action 6.4:** Fine-tuning of innovative solutions developed and deployed at CI operators in terms of functionality, technical and operational robustness, alignment to standards and regulations, as well as to the evolution of the state of the art.

Figure 9: Overview of the Research and Technology Development Roadmap.

7. Conclusions and Outlook

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

This report marks another significant step toward achieving the overarching goals of the EU-CIP project's information analysis activities: identifying capability gaps in Critical Infrastructure Protection and Resilience (CIP/CIR), analysing technological advancements to address these gaps, and providing actionable roadmaps to guide the development, validation, commercialization, and adoption of essential technologies.

Building on previous analyses, this edition delivers:

- **Updated Insights on Capability Needs and Gaps:**
The report presents the latest understanding of capability gaps in CIP/CIR, including those arising from rapid technological change, climate impacts, and disruptive global events such as wars and pandemics. This expanded perspective enhances and extends the gaps identified in earlier reports.
- **Comprehensive Technology Analysis:**
A broad range of technologies is examined—from infrastructure solutions like Cloud/Edge and 5G/6G, to AI-driven tools, UAVs, and advanced cybersecurity measures. The report also explores how these technologies can be integrated to strengthen the cyber resilience of critical infrastructures.
- **Strategic Roadmap for Research and Innovation:**
A clear roadmap is provided to guide research, innovation, standards development, and commercialization activities in the most relevant technology areas.

In addition, the report highlights complementary assets that enhance the value and interoperability of these technologies, including relevant standards and essential skills profiles needed to effectively address identified gaps.

The findings are based on a robust methodology that combines stakeholder consultation, desk research, and market analysis—ensuring a well-rounded and actionable foundation for future editions of the roadmap series.

This report is accompanied by sector-specific whitepapers on CIP/CIR research and development, offering targeted insights for increasing the resilience of critical entities in sectors such as finance, water, telecommunications, and space. These whitepapers are designed to provide foresight and practical guidance to stakeholders, including policymakers. Future editions will expand this coverage to additional sectors and provide updated insights as new needs and challenges emerge.

By continuously updating and deepening this analysis, the EU-CIP project aims to equip the CIP/CIR community with the knowledge, tools, and strategic direction needed to build a more secure, resilient, and adaptive critical infrastructure ecosystem for Europe and beyond.

8. References

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9. Annex A: Status of CIP/CIR

9.1. Annex A.1: Elaboration on State-of-the-Art Technologies

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

- **Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence:**

- Description: Cyber-physical threat intelligence refers to the process of collecting, analysing, and sharing information about threats that target systems integrating physical and digital elements. These threats can include attacks on industrial control systems (ICS), operational technology (OT) networks, and other critical infrastructure components.
- Benefits: Offers early detection of potential threats and vulnerabilities, proactive implementation of security measures by understanding emerging threats and attack vectors, informed decision making (prioritise security investments and allocate resources effectively), fosters collaboration and collective defence against cyber-physical threats, enables organisations to respond swiftly to security incidents, minimizing the impact on critical infrastructure operations.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Provides timely insights into emerging threats, enabling proactive defence measures, facilitating incident response efforts, supporting compliance with regulatory requirements and promoting collaboration among security stakeholders.

- **Security Risk Assessment:**

- Description: Security risk assessment involves the systematic evaluation of threats, vulnerabilities, and potential impacts on an organisation's critical assets and infrastructure. It typically includes identifying assets, assessing threats and vulnerabilities, analysing risks, and developing mitigation strategies to address identified weaknesses.
- Benefits: Helps organisations identify and prioritise critical assets and systems, prioritise risks based on their likelihood and potential impact on critical operations, allocate resources and invest effectively, monitor changes in the threat landscape promoting continuous improvement in security measures.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Helps identifying vulnerabilities in critical infrastructure systems (including physical, cyber, and human factors), CIs may anticipate and prepare for various scenarios that may impact critical infrastructure operations, enable organisations to develop and implement mitigation strategies, allows organisations to develop resilience plans and contingency measures to maintain critical operations.

- **Impact assessment Tools:**

- Description: Impact assessment tools are methodologies, frameworks, or software applications used to assess the potential effects (including financial losses, operational downtime, regulatory penalties, reputational damage, and public safety risks) of security incidents, disruptions, or changes on critical infrastructure assets, services, and stakeholders. These tools help organisations quantify and qualify the impact of various scenarios to inform decision-making and risk management strategies.
- Benefits: Provide insights into the potential consequences of security incidents or disruptions, through quantifying the potential impact of different scenarios, organisations can prioritise mitigation efforts and allocate resources effectively, assist CIs in identifying the resources required to mitigate and recover from security incidents, enable stakeholders to make informed choices regarding risk tolerance, security investments, and resilience strategies.

- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Helps identifying, analysing, and prioritizing potential impacts on assets/operations/stakeholders, enables CIs to develop resilience plans and business continuity strategies, prioritise remediation efforts and implement effective security controls, support training and simulation exercises by simulating various security scenarios and evaluating the effectiveness of response plans, incident management procedures, and recovery strategies.
- **Digital Twins:**
 - Description: A digital twin is a virtual representation of an infrastructure that encapsulates physical objects, processes, or systems and mimics the behaviour, characteristics, and interactions of physical assets, processes, or systems in real-time or near real-time. This representation is based on either a 2D or a 3D model that demonstrates both physical and data flows within the infrastructure. Real-time data from sensors, equipment, or assets are registered within the digital twin. Artificial intelligence, advanced analytics, and modelling techniques are employed to simulate their behaviour and characteristics. Essentially, digital twins provide a digital counterpart to physical entities, allowing for real-time monitoring, analysis, and optimization. Digital twins can be utilised to offer significant benefits to their owners. They can provide insights into the performance and behaviour of physical assets or processes, enabling better-informed decision-making based on real-time data. By continuously monitoring and analysing data from both digital and physical assets, digital twins can predict potential failures, ill-designed procedures, or maintenance needs, allowing organizations to schedule maintenance activities proactively, reduce downtime, and optimize asset performance. Different scenarios can be simulated leading to the development of optimized processes for efficiency, productivity, and cost-effectiveness. Risks can be identified and mitigated, effectively, enhancing safety and reliability. Finally, resource usage, such as energy, materials, or manpower can be optimised leading to cost savings and sustainability benefits. In the context of Critical Infrastructure Protection efforts, digital twins can support Enhanced Security enabling organizations to simulate and analyse potential security threats or vulnerabilities, allowing the design of proactive measures to strengthen security and resilience. Risk Assessment and Management can be achieved by identifying potential weaknesses, testing, and implementing appropriate safeguards. This is achieved by planning and executing simulation exercises to prepare for and respond to various disaster scenarios, ensuring operational continuity and rapid recovery in such cases. Finally, Regulatory Compliance can be achieved by providing accurate data and insights into the performance and security of critical infrastructure systems, supporting audit processes and reporting. Overall, digital twins offer significant potential to enhance the resilience, efficiency, and security of critical infrastructure systems, supporting CIP efforts in various ways.
 - Benefits: Enable real-time monitoring and analysis of critical infrastructure assets and systems, providing insights into their performance, condition, and behaviour; Predict potential failures, identify maintenance needs, and optimize asset performance to prevent costly downtime and disruptions; Facilitate optimization of critical infrastructure operations by simulating different scenarios, evaluating alternative strategies, and identifying opportunities for improvement; Support risk management efforts by assessing the impact of potential threats, vulnerabilities, and disruptions.

- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Enable organisations to manage and monitor critical infrastructure assets more effectively; Support resilience planning by simulating various scenarios, assessing the impact of disruptive events, and identifying strategies to mitigate risks and enhance recovery capabilities; assess cybersecurity risks and vulnerabilities in critical infrastructure systems, allowing organisations to implement proactive security measures; enhance situational awareness by providing a comprehensive view of critical infrastructure operations; facilitate collaboration among stakeholders by providing a common platform for data sharing, analysis, and decision-making.
- **Anomaly Detection:**
 - Description: Anomaly detection involves the use of statistical, machine learning, or data mining techniques to automatically identify deviations, outliers, or unusual patterns within datasets or systems. It aims to distinguish between normal behaviour and anomalous behaviour, which may indicate potential security threats, system failures, or irregular activities.
 - Benefits: Enable (near) real-time detection of security threats, system failures, and operational abnormalities; helps reduce false positive alerts and focus attention on genuine security incidents; automates the process of monitoring and analysing vast amounts of data; enhances situational awareness by providing insights into emerging threats, vulnerabilities, and performance issues.
 - Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Helps CIs detect and respond to cyber threats, including malware infections, data breaches, insider threats, and unauthorised access attempts; assists in the detection and diagnosis of faults, failures, and malfunctions in critical infrastructure components, such as power grids, transportation systems, and industrial control systems; supports predictive maintenance initiatives and avoid unplanned downtime by identifying anomalies in equipment performance, usage patterns, and sensor readings; helps identify fraudulent activities, suspicious transactions, and unusual behaviour patterns indicative; provides valuable insights during incident response efforts, helping security teams prioritise alerts, investigate security incidents, and mitigate the impact of security breaches.
- **Cybersecurity Tools:**
 - Description: Cybersecurity tools are technologies and solutions that help detect, prevent, respond to, and recover from cyber threats and security incidents. These tools encompass a variety of functions, including network security, endpoint protection, threat intelligence, encryption, Security Information and Event Management (SIEM), Identity and Access Management (IAM).
 - Benefits: Enable detection and prevention of a wide range of cyber threats, including malware, ransomware, phishing attacks, insider threats, and advanced persistent threats (APTs); help CIs identify, prioritise, and remediate security vulnerabilities reducing the risk of exploitation and compromise; facilitate incident response and forensic investigations by providing real-time monitoring, analysis, and visibility; assist organisations in complying with industry regulations, data protection laws, and cybersecurity standards; automate routine security tasks improving efficiency, scalability, and consistency in security operations.
 - Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Protect critical infrastructure networks from unauthorised access, malicious traffic, and cyber-attacks; Support safeguarding

critical infrastructure endpoints from malware infections, data breaches, and unauthorised access; aggregate, correlate, and analyse security logs and event data from across critical infrastructure systems and applications to detect and investigate security incidents in real-time; ensure that only authorised personnel can access sensitive information and perform privileged actions; protect critical infrastructure assets from unauthorised disclosure, tampering, and theft, through encryption and data loss prevention; help CIs proactively defend against cyber-attacks and mitigate security risks.

- **Modelling of cascading effects and interdependencies between CIs:**

- Description: Modelling cascading effects and interdependencies involves creating computational models that simulate the interactions and dependencies between different components, systems, and sectors within critical infrastructure networks. These models capture how disruptions or failures in one part of the infrastructure can propagate across interconnected systems, leading to cascading effects and broader impacts on essential services and societal functions.
- Benefits: Enable assessing the potential consequences of disruptions or failures within critical infrastructure systems, identifying high-risk scenarios and vulnerabilities that may require mitigation; support the development of efficient resilience plans and contingency measures to mitigate the impact of disruptions, maintain critical operations, and facilitate rapid recovery; understanding interdependencies helps CIs prioritise investments and allocate resources effectively; Fosters collaboration and coordination among stakeholders by promoting a shared understanding of risks and priorities; provide with insights into the complex interactions and dependencies between infrastructure systems, supporting informed decision-making.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Supports identification of key nodes, pathways, and vulnerabilities that may propagate disruptions or failures across interconnected systems; enables CIs to simulate various scenarios, such as natural disasters, cyber-attacks, or supply chain disruptions, and assess their potential impact on critical infrastructure operations and services; quantify the potential consequences of disruptions, including economic losses, public safety risks, and societal impacts, helping organisations prioritise mitigation efforts and allocate resources to reduce overall risk; build redundancy, resilience, and adaptive capacity into critical infrastructure systems to withstand and recover from disruptions; support the increase of policies, regulations, and standards aimed at enhancing the resilience and security of critical infrastructure networks / supply chains.

- **Advances in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning:**

- Description: Artificial Intelligence (AI) with its subset of Machine Learning (ML) refers to the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, particularly computer systems. These processes solve tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as natural language processing, problem-solving, pattern recognition, and decision-making. The processes also include learning, reasoning, problem-solving, perception, and decision-making. AI systems are designed to analyse large amounts of data, recognize patterns, and make predictions or decisions autonomously. AI algorithms can analyse large and complex datasets to extract valuable insights, trends, and patterns that enable data-driven decision-making. AI can be utilised to predict future events based on historical data and patterns, a.k.a. predictive analytics. This allows

organisations to anticipate and mitigate risks, optimize operations, and improve resource allocation. AI algorithms can also perform tasks and processes with a high level of accuracy and consistency, automating them, reducing errors and operational costs associated with manual labour. Finally, AI systems can personalize user experiences, services, and recommendations by analysing user behaviour and preferences, enhancing customer satisfaction and engagement. In the context of Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) efforts, artificial intelligence can support multiple functions. AI systems can analyse large volumes of data from various sources, such as surveillance cameras, sensors, and cybersecurity logs, to detect and identify potential security threats, anomalies, or malicious activities. AI can also be used to assess the vulnerability of critical infrastructure systems by analysing factors such as physical security measures, network configurations, and software vulnerabilities, helping organisations identify and prioritise security risks. Cybersecurity is another domain that can profit from AI. AI-powered cybersecurity solutions can detect, prevent, and respond to cyber threats in real-time, including malware, phishing attacks, and insider threats, enhancing the resilience of critical infrastructure networks and systems. Finally, AI systems can assist in incident response and recovery efforts by providing real-time alerts, recommendations, and automate actions to mitigate the impact of security incidents or disruptions on critical infrastructure operations. Overall, artificial intelligence offers valuable capabilities to enhance the security, resilience, and efficiency of critical infrastructure systems, supporting CIP efforts by providing advanced analytics, threat detection, and decision support capabilities.

- Benefits: AI and ML algorithms can analyse large datasets to detect anomalies and patterns indicative of cyber threats or physical intrusions; ML models can forecast future trends, identify potential vulnerabilities, and predict security incidents based on historical data, enabling organisations to proactively address security risks and mitigate potential impacts; AI-driven automation streamlines security operations by automating routine tasks, such as threat detection, incident response, and remediation, freeing up human analysts to focus on more complex and strategic activities; ML algorithms continuously learn and adapt to evolving threats and attack techniques, enabling security systems to dynamically adjust their defences and detect previously unseen threats in real-time; AI-powered analytics provide decision-makers with actionable insights and recommendations based on data-driven analysis, helping organisations prioritise security investments, allocate resources effectively, and respond to security incidents more efficiently.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: AI and ML enable organisations to analyse large volumes of threat intelligence data, identify emerging trends, and prioritise threats based on their relevance and potential impact on critical infrastructure systems; ML algorithms can analyse user behaviour, network traffic patterns, and system activity to detect abnormal behaviour indicative of insider threats, unauthorised access, or malicious activities targeting critical infrastructure assets; ML-based anomaly detection algorithms identify deviations from normal patterns or behaviours within critical infrastructure systems, helping detect security breaches, system failures, and operational abnormalities in real-time; AI-driven predictive maintenance models analyse sensor data and equipment telemetry to forecast potential failures, optimize maintenance schedules, and reduce downtime in critical infrastructure systems; Natural Language Processing (NLP) enable organisations to analyse unstructured data, such as security reports, incident logs, and threat

intelligence feeds, extracting actionable insights and facilitating information sharing and collaboration among stakeholders.

- **Unmanned Vehicles and Robots:**

- Description: Unmanned vehicles and robots refer to a wide range of autonomous or remotely controlled machines that operate without direct human intervention. These machines can include aerial drones, ground-based robots, and underwater vehicles, among others. They serve various purposes and applications, providing benefits such as safe operations in hazardous or dangerous environments, reducing the risk to human personnel involved in critical infrastructure protection efforts. They can also boost cost effectiveness performing labour-intensive or high-risk operations faster and at a lower cost. Unmanned vehicles and robots can work autonomously or under remote control, enabling them to perform tasks more quickly and efficiently than human workers, thereby increasing overall productivity. Additionally, they are extremely versatile having the ability to have as a payload various sensors, cameras, and manipulators, enabling them to perform a wide range of tasks, from surveillance and monitoring to inspection, maintenance, and response. Their ability to access hard-to-reach or remote areas, such as confined spaces, elevated structures, or underwater environments, allows them to provide comprehensive coverage and assessment of critical infrastructure assets. In the context of Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) efforts, unmanned vehicles and robots can support surveillance and monitoring missions using aerial drones and ground-based robots equipped with cameras and sensors can patrol critical infrastructure sites, providing real-time surveillance to detect and deter security threats, intrusions, or unauthorised activities. These may include patrolling the perimeter of critical infrastructure facilities to detect potential security breaches or perimeter intrusions, as well as environmental monitoring such as the assessment of air quality, water quality, and radiation levels around critical infrastructure sites, helping to ensure compliance with regulatory requirements and detect potential environmental threats. They can be used also for conducting regular inspections of critical infrastructure assets, such as pipelines, power lines, bridges, and buildings, to identify defects, damage, or vulnerabilities, enabling proactive maintenance and risk mitigation. In cases of disaster, they can be deployed rapidly to disaster-affected areas to assess damage, search for survivors, and provide situational awareness to emergency responders, facilitating more effective and coordinated response efforts. Overall, unmanned vehicles and robots offer valuable capabilities to enhance the security, resilience, and efficiency of critical infrastructure systems, supporting CIP efforts by providing cost-effective, versatile, and accessible solutions for surveillance, inspection, and response.
- Benefits: Provide surveillance capabilities, quickly cover large areas and access hard-to-reach or hazardous locations, enhancing situational awareness and threat detection capabilities; offer rapid deployment and mobility, enabling swift response to security incidents; offer a variety of data collection and analysis capabilities (sensors, thermal/day/night cameras, CBRN, etc.); in case of drones cost-effective alternatives to traditional manned aircraft and ground-based surveillance methods; enhance safety for personnel by minimizing the need for manual inspections in hazardous or inaccessible environments.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Enable visual inspections of critical infrastructure components, such as bridges, pipelines, power lines, and

communication towers, identifying defects, damage, or anomalies that require repair or maintenance; provide real-time surveillance and monitoring of critical infrastructure sites, detecting security breaches, unauthorised access, and suspicious activities; support emergency response and disaster management efforts by conducting search and rescue operations, damage assessments, and situational assessments in disaster-affected areas; monitor environmental conditions, emissions, and pollution levels around critical infrastructure facilities; used for training exercises and simulations to prepare personnel for emergency scenarios, security threats, and crisis situations, enhancing readiness, coordination, and response capabilities.

- **Resilient communication networks:**

- Resilient communications refer to communication systems and technologies that are designed to remain operational and reliable even during adverse conditions or disruptions. These systems play a crucial role in Critical Infrastructure Protection efforts by ensuring that essential communication channels remain available for coordination, response, and recovery activities. Resilient communication systems help maintain connectivity between critical infrastructure operators, emergency responders, and stakeholders during emergencies or disasters, ensuring continuity of essential services and operations. They can also empower situational awareness by ensuring communication with responders, sensors, and data providers on the field and beyond. Redundancy and backup, such as alternative communication pathways, satellite links, or mesh networks, to ensure that communication remains available even if primary channels are disrupted or compromised, is an essential requirement. Robust security measures, such as encryption and authentication mechanisms, to protect sensitive information and prevent unauthorized access or tampering, enhancing the security of critical infrastructure communications is also required.
- In the context of Critical Infrastructure Protection efforts, resilient communications can facilitate coordination and response by ensuring the ability to share critical information and allocate resources effectively during emergencies or disruptions. Stakeholders can have timely and accurate information about the status of critical infrastructure assets, potential threats, and response activities, enhancing situational awareness and decision-making capabilities. Communications must be interoperable among different agencies, organizations, and jurisdictions, enabling seamless communication and collaboration across diverse stakeholders. Resilient communication technologies allow operators to remotely monitor and control critical infrastructure assets, such as power grids, transportation networks, and water treatment facilities, enhancing operational efficiency and resilience.
- Overall, resilient communications are essential for safeguarding critical infrastructure systems and ensuring effective response and recovery capabilities in the face of emergencies, disasters, or security threats.

- **Blockchain in CIP:**

- Description: Blockchain is a distributed ledger technology that records transactions across a network of computers in a secure, transparent, and tamper-resistant manner. Each block in the blockchain contains a cryptographic hash of the previous block, creating a chain of blocks that are linked together and immutable.
- Benefits: Transactions recorded on the blockchain are immutable and cannot be altered or deleted once they are confirmed, ensuring the integrity and authenticity of

critical infrastructure data and transactions; operates on a decentralised network of nodes, eliminating the need for a central authority or intermediary to validate transactions, reducing single points of failure and enhancing system resilience; enables stakeholders to trace the history of transactions, verify the authenticity of data, and ensure compliance with regulatory requirements and industry standards; uses cryptographic techniques to secure transactions and prevent unauthorised access or tampering, enhancing the security and integrity of critical infrastructure systems and information; support smart contracts, self-executing contracts with predefined rules and conditions, enabling automated and secure execution of agreements, transactions, and business processes.

- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Enables end-to-end visibility and traceability of goods and materials across the supply chain, mitigating risks related to counterfeit products, supply chain disruptions, and unauthorised modifications; Blockchain-based identity management solutions offer secure and decentralised identity verification, authentication, and access control mechanisms, reducing the risk of identity theft, fraud, and unauthorised access to critical infrastructure systems; provides a secure and immutable platform for storing and sharing sensitive data, ensuring data integrity, confidentiality, and protection against unauthorised modifications or data breaches; enable secure and decentralised sharing of threat intelligence data, facilitating collaboration among stakeholders.

- **Internet of Things (IoT) Security Solutions:**

- Description: IoT security solutions include encryption, authentication mechanisms, and continuous monitoring to secure IoT devices and networks.
- Benefits: Mitigates risks associated with IoT devices, such as unauthorised access, data breaches, and device manipulation.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Ensures the security and reliability of interconnected devices and systems within critical infrastructure networks, reducing the likelihood of cyber-attacks and operational disruptions.

- **Big Data Analytics:**

- Description: Big data analytics processes and analyses large volumes of data to identify patterns, trends, and anomalies.
- Benefits: Helps in identifying potential threats, predicting system failures, and optimizing operational efficiency.
- Support for safeguarding Critical Infrastructure Protection: Enables real-time monitoring, threat detection, and risk assessment across diverse data sources within critical infrastructure environments, improving situational awareness and incident response capabilities.

- **Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) Security:**

- Description: CPS security focuses on securing the interaction between physical components and computer systems in critical infrastructure.
- Benefits: Protects against cyber-attacks targeting physical infrastructure components, such as industrial control systems and operational technology.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Enhances the resilience of critical infrastructure systems against cyber threats, ensuring the integrity, availability, and safety of essential services and operations.

- **Advanced Encryption Techniques:**

- Description: Advanced encryption techniques employ sophisticated cryptographic algorithms to secure sensitive data and communications.
- Benefits: Provides confidentiality, integrity, and authenticity of information transmitted and stored within critical infrastructure networks.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: safeguards sensitive data, communications, and transactions against unauthorised access, interception, and tampering, reducing the risk of data breaches and cyber-attacks.

- **Integrated Security Platforms / Converged Security Information Management (CSIM):**

- Description: CSIM platforms integrate data from diverse security systems, including video surveillance, access control, intrusion detection, perimeter security, and cybersecurity tools, into a centralised management system. These platforms use advanced analytics, automation, and visualization capabilities to correlate events, detect anomalies, and enable real-time situational awareness across critical infrastructure environments.
- Benefits: Provide a centralised interface for managing and monitoring multiple security systems and devices, streamlining security operations and reducing the complexity of managing disparate security solutions; offer a unified view (situational awareness) of security events, incidents, and alarms across critical infrastructure facilities; use advanced correlation and analysis techniques to identify patterns, trends, and relationships between security events and incidents, helping organisations prioritise threats, allocate resources, and implement appropriate response measures; automate routine security tasks, such as event triage, incident escalation, and response coordination, enabling faster response times; integrate with external systems, such as emergency response services, law enforcement agencies, and third-party security providers, facilitating collaboration and information sharing.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Enable comprehensive monitoring of critical infrastructure facilities, assets, and perimeters; leverage advanced analytics and machine learning algorithms to detect and prevent security threats, including physical intrusions, cyber-attacks, unauthorised access attempts; streamline incident response and management processes by providing real-time alerts, automated workflows, and collaboration tools for coordinating response efforts and communicating with stakeholders.

- **Physical Security Technologies:**

- Description: Physical security technologies include access control systems, surveillance cameras, and intrusion detection sensors to protect against physical threats.
- Benefits: Deters unauthorised access, detects security breaches, and enhances situational awareness of physical infrastructure assets.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Safeguards critical infrastructure facilities, assets, and personnel from physical threats, vandalism, sabotage, and unauthorised entry.

- **Cloud Security Solutions:**

- Description: Cloud security solutions offer scalable and resilient protection for critical infrastructure systems hosted in cloud environments.
- Benefits: Provides data encryption, identity and access management, and threat intelligence services to secure cloud-based infrastructure and applications.
- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Ensures the confidentiality, availability, and integrity of critical data and applications hosted in cloud environments, reducing exposure to cyber threats and data breaches.

- **Collaborative Defence Mechanisms:**
 - Description: Collaborative defence mechanisms involve sharing threat intelligence, best practices, and resources among government agencies, private sector entities, and cybersecurity organisations.
 - Benefits: Enhances collective resilience against cyber threats, fosters information sharing and coordination, and facilitates timely response to emerging threats.
 - Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Strengthens collaborative efforts to identify, analyse, and mitigate cyber threats targeting critical infrastructure, promoting a more robust and coordinated defence posture.

- **CBRN detection, decontamination, and neutralization technologies**
 - Description: CBRN detection technologies encompass a range of sensors, instruments, and systems designed to detect the presence of agents in the environment. Decontamination technologies involve methods and equipment designed to remove or neutralize hazardous contaminants from personnel, equipment, and infrastructure.
 - Benefits: CBRN detection systems provide early warning of potential threats, enabling timely response and mitigation measures; By monitoring for CBRN threats in real-time, detection technologies enhance situational awareness; protect personnel from exposure to harmful contaminants, minimizing the risk of injury, illness, or long-term health effects; Effective neutralization minimizes the environmental impact.
 - Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Some CBRN detection systems offer remote monitoring capabilities, allowing for continuous surveillance of critical infrastructure sites and remote areas where personnel access may be limited; Integration with command and control systems enables seamless coordination between detection, response, and emergency management teams; Effective decontamination helps safeguard critical infrastructure assets and facilities, reducing the potential for contamination spread and ensuring the continuity of essential services.

- **Counter-UAS / Anti-drone solutions:**
 - Description: Counter-UAS solutions encompass a variety of technologies, systems, and methodologies developed to counter the unauthorised or hostile use of drones. These solutions employ detection sensors, surveillance equipment, electronic countermeasures, and physical mitigation techniques to neutralize or mitigate the threat posed by rogue drones.
 - Benefits: Help mitigate the potential threats posed by unauthorised or malicious drone activity; provide early detection and warning of drone threats, allowing security personnel to respond promptly; enhance situational awareness by monitoring airspace activity, detecting unauthorised drones; scalable and adaptable to diverse

environments and operational requirements, allowing for the deployment of tailored countermeasures.

- Support for Critical Infrastructure Protection: Protect critical infrastructure airspace and perimeter from unauthorised or malicious drone activity, including security breaches, privacy violations, surveillance, smuggling, and physical attacks; provide event security and crowd management capabilities by monitoring airspace activity during public gatherings, special events, and high-profile functions; safeguard data privacy and protection by preventing unauthorized drone surveillance, reconnaissance, or data collection activities targeting sensitive information, personnel, or proprietary assets.

9.2. Annex A.2: Review of existing capability gaps and needs

The information analysis and workshops conducted as part of the EU-CIP project have identified a range of capability needs and gaps within CIP/CIR (Table 12) that require immediate attention to enhance the security, resilience, and adaptability of Europe’s critical infrastructures.

The identified capability needs span across enhanced adaptability to new threats, reduced response times, increased transparency of solutions, improved detection capabilities, and improved risk and impact assessment capabilities, among others. These needs highlight the importance of developing systems and strategies that can rapidly adapt to and mitigate novel, integrated, and asymmetric threats against a backdrop of increasing reliance on sophisticated technologies and interconnected critical infrastructure systems.

Table 12: Current Capability Needs and Gaps

Capability Needs (C)	Capability Gaps (CG)
C1 - Enhanced adaptability	CG1 - Poor Automation
C2 - Reduced Response Times	CG2 – Lack of proper control of Interconnectedness
C3 - Increased Transparency	CG3 – Poor Alignment of Resilience Indicators
C4 - Improved Detection Capabilities	CG4 – Lack of agreed Standards-based stress-testing procedures
C5 - Improved risk and impact assessment capabilities	CG5 – Problems with the classification of IoT Devices
C6 - Better integration of Telco Security tools with Information Security Management tools	CG6 – Scalability in the Mitigation of Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks
C7 – Solutions addressing cascading effects between different entities and states	CG7 – Development and Deployment of AI-based systems
C8 - Transformation of proactive and adaptive protection tools and methods to incorporate real-time functionalities	CG8 – Lack of Holistic Security Management Systems
C9 – Better exploitation of information from critical sensors towards augmented situation awareness	CG9 – Gaps in Emergency Management Processes

Capability Needs (C)	Capability Gaps (CG)
C10 – Risk prediction and anticipation	CG10 – Inability to cope with dynamically evolving threats
C11 – Training, Reskilling and Upskilling	CG11 – Poor Awareness about modern CIP/CIR challenges
C12 - Supply Chain Security	CG12 – Adaptive Threat Intelligence
C13 - Public-Private Collaboration Frameworks	CG13 - Incident Response Coordination
C14 - Cross-Border Coordination	CG14 - Emerging Technology Adoption
C15 - Business Continuity and Disaster Recovery (BCDR)	CG15 - Rapid Recovery Strategies
C16 - Resilience Metrics and Reporting	

Among the critical gaps identified are **poor automation in cybersecurity processes, lack of control over interconnected assets and their dependencies, misalignment of resilience indicators, lack of standardised stress-testing procedures, and difficulties in the classification and secure management of IoT devices.** These gaps underscore vulnerabilities such as delayed threat detection and response, inefficient resource allocation, and increased risk of cascading failures across interconnected infrastructures.

The workshops and stakeholder inputs further emphasize the necessity of addressing these capability gaps through integration and avoiding silos, adopting and integrating emerging technologies like AI and blockchain, and developing rapid recovery strategies. Additionally, there is a recognized need for enhancing awareness about contemporary CIP/CIR challenges, developing adaptive threat intelligence, and ensuring effective incident response coordination.

Prioritization of these gaps, particularly those not adequately covered is crucial. Emphasizing gaps such as adaptive threat intelligence, rapid recovery strategies, development and deployment of AI-based systems, and enhancing control over interconnectedness can significantly contribute to bolstering CIP/CIR. By focusing on these areas, stakeholders can allocate resources more effectively, fostering a resilient, secure, and adaptive infrastructure ecosystem capable of withstanding and rapidly responding to evolving threats and challenges. Addressing the identified capability needs and gaps through concerted efforts involving the adoption of advanced technologies, enhancing interconnectivity and transparency, and prioritizing rapid recovery and adaptive threat intelligence, is essential for the future-proofing of Europe’s critical infrastructures against an increasingly complex threat landscape. Collaboration among government, industry, academia, and international partners is key to developing comprehensive, integrated, and flexible strategies that ensure the security and resilience of critical infrastructure systems.

9.2.1. Research Initiatives with the Potential to Address Existing Capability Gaps

Looking at the capability gaps identified in the roadmap v2 there are research initiatives that have the potential to address them. The information provided here will focus primarily on artificial intelligence as the most versatile technology.

- **CG1 – Poor Automation:** Recent rapid development in AI technologies have the potential to significantly contribute to addressing the capability gap of poor automation when it comes to achieving fast detection, protection, and recovery from cyberattacks. Indeed, while it may not be economically rational to build AI systems for some industries or activities, given its digital nature, the cyber domain pop up as perfect to do so. Importantly, the deployment of AI technologies by cybercriminals increases, making their attacks much more efficient, agile and dangerous. In fact, the ability to automate the search for vulnerable elements of the system via AI likely opens infinite attack scenarios, many of which may be even difficult to imagine or comprehend by humans. Hence, to combat such threats, it is necessary to build dedicated AI cybersecurity solutions. As far as the scientific research is concerned, a review by Kaur et al. [4] from 2022 summarises the literature on the use of AI in cybersecurity with a particular focus on practical applications within five different cybersecurity functions: Identify, Protect, Detect, Respond and Recover (as defined by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) cybersecurity framework [5]). In more detail:
 - The Identify function involves understanding, identifying, and managing cybersecurity risks to systems, assets, data, and capabilities. The current literature proposes AI-based solutions to automate the following activities of this kind: asset inventory management, configuration management, security control validation, business impact analysis, policy enforcement, and vulnerability identification and assessment, threat hunting, path modelling, risk analysis and impact assessment, predictive intelligence, decision support for risk planning, risk management.
 - The Protect function involves on planning and implementing appropriate tools to limit or contain the impact of a potential cyber-attack. Sample AI-based solutions concern automated access control, AI-supported user and device authentication, adaptive security awareness and training.
 - The Detect function concerns the identification of cybersecurity incidents, impact assessment, and the implementation of monitoring to verify the effectiveness of any protective measures undertaken. The AI-based solutions for this function include classification of threats, data processing and correlation for situational awareness, automated analysis of various sources including dark web content for proactive threat intelligence.
 - The Respond function is meant to manage the impact to a potential cybersecurity event. It involves planning processes to analyse the incidents to determine their cause, scope and impact, contain the damage, and coordinate the actions during and after an attack. AI is an obvious technology of choice to automate such processes. In particular, it can be used to dynamically manage cases, automate responsibility allocation and collaboration management, automate alert triage and forensic analysis, for automated mitigation, remediation, and introducing long-term improvements via automated knowledge extraction.
 - The Recover function is meant to maintain resilience despite past and ongoing cybersecurity incident. The application of AI techniques in this area remains relatively underexplored. A few studies focus on the analysis and aggregation of incident reports to understand the vulnerabilities ex post.

More details can be found in Table 4-8 in the review by [4]. The authors also pinpoint several emerging areas in cybersecurity where the application of AI-based solutions holds great promise and appears indispensable, although they have yet to materialize. These include among others automated retrieval of key risk indicators, defending against zero-day attacks, predictive and multi-lingual intelligence, data breach prevention and discovery, protection against fake document generation.

- **CG2 - Lack of proper control of Interconnectedness:** The AI technology can be leveraged to optimize complex interconnected systems of critical infrastructures. A few analyses of such systems can be found in the literature. For example, [6] considers how AI technology can address the challenges related to large-scale construction and operation projects, such as the maintenance of bridges and power plants, that can involve thousands of spatially and temporally distributed operation activities. Such problems involve physical facilities, operation systems, and human behaviours and their complexity renders traditional computational approaches obsolete. Instead, AI methods (machine learning and symbolic reasoning techniques in particular) can be used to detect and resolve reliability issues in civil infrastructure construction, maintenance, and operation processes. Another example is the PRAETORIAN framework proposed by [7] to be used by security managers of critical infrastructures to detect and mitigate cyber, physical, and combined security threats to specific critical infrastructure sites and their interrelated counterparts. The framework features advanced physical and cyber-domain situation awareness tools, a component to forecast the cascading effects of ongoing incidents and their impact on interconnected sites, and a tool with advanced automation capabilities for detecting and mitigating cyber and physical threats across various types of sites.
- **CG4 - Lack of agreed Standards-based stress-testing procedures:** [8] proposed a tiered approach to stress testing critical infrastructure as a part of the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) Principles for Resilient Infrastructure [9]. Their approach, inspired by Basel stress testing for the financial sector [10], utilizes advanced modelling techniques based on network science and AI to assess cascading effects in interconnected critical infrastructure systems (modelled as networks) in response to random and targeted threats and attack scenarios. Specifically, their highest-level stress test (Tier 3) is the most granular assessment of a critical infrastructure system's response to disruption from cascading failures. Its goal is to map the entire system and to identify possible improvements to its individual components. The solution combines network science, agent-based modelling, artificial intelligence, or advanced mathematics.
- **CG5 – Problems with the classification of IoT Devices:** [11] proposed a system based on Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) that categorizes IoT devices (into IoT devices that are malicious, non-IoT devices that are malicious, and other man-in-the-middle traffic sources) and identifies security-related issues.

9.3. Annex A.3: New Capability Needs and Gaps

A second round of internal consultation aiming to update the current list of capability gaps and needs within CIP/CIR was launched since the issue of the last EU-CIP roadmap (v2) and, according to the responses received to the questionnaire, several key themes emerged. These insights not only reinforce existing understanding but also underline areas that require attention:

9.3.1. New and emerging Capability Needs

- **C17 – Secure Information Exchange:** The necessity for secure channels to facilitate the exchange of security-related information among security-related projects and CI/Critical Entity (CE) underscores the growing interdependence of critical infrastructures and the need for collaborative security efforts.
- **C18 – Artificial Intelligence Integration:** Broadening the application of artificial intelligence across all CIP/CIR domains to bolster threat detection, prediction, and response capabilities.
- **C19 – Global Resilience Activities:** With cybersecurity needs escalating, a cohesive effort to integrate the management of physical, digital, and natural event domains is crucial for a unified resilience strategy and to address the complex nature of current threats.
- **C20 – Infrastructure Resiliency against Climate Change:** Investing in infrastructure capable of withstanding and quickly recovering from extreme weather events induced by climate change. Due to climate change, the CIP/CIR sector must consider how extreme weather events may affect essential infrastructure. This necessitates making investments in infrastructure that can withstand harm and bounce back from occurrences faster.
- **C21 – Improved Supply Chain Collaboration:** It is fundamental to improve cooperation among the involved stakeholders in order to adopt a cohesive strategy to identify vulnerabilities, share information on potential threats and coordinate responses to potential disruptions in the supply chain.
- **C22 – Mapping IT and OT interdependencies:** Identifying the connections between IT and OT systems in terms of security and resilience is crucial for improving the overall protection and resilience of infrastructure.

9.3.2. New and emerging Capability Gaps

- **CG16 – Interlaced Domain Integration:** There's a highlighted need for better connectivity and integration across physical, digital, and natural domains to address complex, multifaceted threats and to create a holistic defence mechanism against these threats.
- **CG17 – Remote Work Cybersecurity:** The transition to remote work has exposed new weaknesses, highlighting the vital need for enhanced cybersecurity protocols designed to safeguard decentralised essential infrastructure networks.
- **CG18 – Supply Chain Vulnerabilities:** The epidemic has revealed gaps in global supply networks, highlighting the need for strong systems to guarantee the uninterrupted and dependable provision of essential infrastructure services. Recognizing and addressing vulnerabilities within the global supply network to ensure the reliability of critical infrastructure operations.
- **CG19 – Emergency Preparedness (incorporating Pandemic Planning):** The latest pandemic highlights the need of integrating thorough pandemic planning into current disaster

preparation and response methods for CIP/CIR sectors. The pandemic has pointed to the significance of emergency preparedness. The current catastrophic preparedness methods used in the CIP/CIR area need to incorporate pandemic planning, response, and recovery.

- **CG20 – Aging Infrastructure Monitoring:** Addressing the challenge of monitoring ageing infrastructure, which is sometimes arduous and expensive, but essential for maintaining service continuity and safety.
- **CG21 – Crisis and Cyber-Physical Threat Intelligence Simulation:** Developing the necessary capabilities for simulating crisis situations and automating the processing of cyber threat intelligence and physical security information.
- **CG22 – AI-Enabled CIP Tool Risks:** Given the emergence of AI-powered CIP/CIR technologies, it is crucial to tackle the particular risks linked to Automated Response, Adaptation, and Reconfiguration in the industrial sector.

To address these gaps and needs, a comprehensive strategy is required, which includes improving secure information exchange protocols, fully incorporating AI capabilities for various applications, and strengthening global resilience efforts. Addressing the new difficulties related to the interconnectedness of different areas, cybersecurity in remote work environments, weaknesses in supply chains, and readiness for pandemics will be essential.

By focusing on these areas, stakeholders within the CIP/CIR domain can significantly advance their strategies to safeguard critical infrastructures against evolving threats and ensure their resilience in the face of unforeseen challenges.

10. Annex B: Evaluation of Tools

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101073878.

10.1. Annex B.1: Current CIP Tools

In the dynamic landscape of Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Critical Infrastructure Resilience (CIR), diverse tools and methods drawn from various categories of the [EU-Civil Security Taxonomy](#) are employed to safeguard Europe's essential services. These tools, integral to daily operational and security protocols, span a wide range of functionalities, covering areas from access control and authentication to monitoring and surveillance, among others.

Among the key tools currently in use are cybersecurity assessments facilitated by Authentication systems (Category #1), market monitoring tools like Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) systems (Category #96), and specialized probes tailored for individual infrastructures. Tools such as RiskRadar, ResilienceTool, and World Economic Forum (WEF) Connectivity Maps offer advanced capabilities for understanding and enhancing the resilience of critical systems, falling under the category of Integrated product security functions (Category #156).

For power systems, n-k contingencies analysis (Category #254) stands out as a critical tool, enabling the maintenance of secure operation even after multiple component failures. Additionally, the segmentation of IT networks (Category #1), multifactor authorization (Category #1), and SIEM tools represent foundational elements in the cybersecurity framework. Other essential tools include Python and Wireguard for secure networking (Category #96), Hyperledger for blockchain applications (Category #96), and digital twins for simulating complex systems (Category #156).

Moreover, the use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) (Category #268), cybersecurity programs (Category #96), and surveillance systems like Closed-Circuit TeleVision (CCTV) (Category #268), along with SCADA systems for utility management (Category #268), showcases the breadth of tools aimed at both cyber and physical security aspects. Risk analysis tools (Category #123), emergency planning software (Category #73), and resilience measurement instruments (Category #123) further contribute to a comprehensive approach towards managing potential risks and preparing for disaster scenarios.

However, the evaluation of these current tools reveals gaps and areas for enhancement, particularly in addressing emerging threats and the evolving landscape of CIP/CIR. The integration of tools like Customs Extended Common Information Sharing Environment (CE-CISE) for communication (Category #65), alongside advanced threat intelligence sharing platforms, underscores the shift towards more interconnected and collaborative security efforts. The development of in-house platforms for Threats and Exposures Management (TEM) (Category #73) and the operations of Security Operations Centres (SOC) (Category #73) highlights the move towards state-of-the-art tailored security solutions.

Emerging tools, such as AI techniques implemented via TensorFlow (Category #96) and Azure digital twins for virtual environment simulation (Category #156), indicate a trend towards leveraging cutting-edge technology to predict, analyse, and mitigate threats more effectively. As these tools evolve, the focus shifts towards improving supply chain collaboration, enhancing interoperability among disparate systems, and fostering a culture of continuous improvement and adaptation to the changing threat landscape.

While the current suite of tools provides a solid foundation for CIP/CIR, continuous evaluation and integration of emerging technologies are essential. This approach will address existing shortcomings, enhance system-wide resilience, and ensure that Europe's critical infrastructures remain robust in the face of new challenges.

10.2. Annex B.2: Analysis of CIP Tools' technological background

A diverse array of technologies is employed in the domains of CIP/CIR to safeguard the critical systems of Europe. These advancements originate from both the European Union (EU) and other regions across the globe, demonstrating a broad array of origins that contribute to the resilience of critical infrastructures.

Among the key technologies utilised are **biometrics, smart card technology, and cryptographic tools developed in the EU**, which form the backbone of secure access, authentication, and data protection strategies.

Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) systems, integral to monitoring and managing security incidents, include solutions from **Microsoft, IBM, Splunk, and Fortinet**. While many SIEM solutions are sourced from **non-European entities**, they are crucial in the real-time analysis of security alerts generated by applications and network hardware. Additionally, frameworks and standards such as **ISO 31000, the Joint Emergency Service Interoperability Programme (JESIP) protocol, and the Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) open standards**, alongside **in-house developed software tools**, underscore the EU's commitment to adopting rigorous methodologies and bespoke solutions for CIP/CIR.

The **n-k contingency analysis**, fully developed within the EU, exemplifies the region's capabilities in ensuring power system resilience. Similarly, tools like the **Open Vulnerability Assessment Scanner (OpenVAS)** for vulnerability assessment and the **Elasticsearch, Logstash, Kibana (ELK) stack** for SIEM-like solutions, also incorporating components from the USA, play a pivotal role in the cybersecurity ecosystem. **Multi-phase resilience assessment tools**, stemming from **EU-funded projects**, illustrate the union's investment in developing advanced methodologies for hazard modelling and impact assessment.

Security Management Systems and other specialized tools, such as **Intrusion Detection Systems** and **Access Control Systems**, though not specified in origin, are integral to securing critical infrastructures. The use of technologies like **ArcGIS, FireEye, Symantec, and SCADA systems** from **Siemens** and **Schneider Electric**, along with **RiskLens** and **Federal Emergency Management Agency's (FEMA) Hazards United States (HAZUS)**, indicates a significant reliance on both **European and American technologies** for a comprehensive approach to CIP/CIR.

Furthermore, the **Risk Analysis and Evaluation Toolkit (RAET) toolkit**, emerging from the EU's STOP-IT project, showcases the union's initiative in addressing cyber-physical threats to water supply networks. The deployment of **Apache products, Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) technologies**, and software like **MatLab** and **Mangold Interact** further highlights the global nature of CIP/CIR technology sources, including contributions from the EU, the USA, China, and other countries.

11. Annex C: Market Analysis, Challenges and Opportunities

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11.1. Annex C.1: Updated Market Analysis

Market Overview

The Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) market is experiencing strong growth, as highlighted by several recent market research reports. For example, Mordor Intelligence forecasts [12] that the global CIP market will increase from approximately USD 148.5 billion in 2024 to USD 191.83 billion by 2029, reflecting a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of over 3.9%. Polaris Research [13] projects a similar growth rate extending through 2030. Additionally, Triton Market Research [14] estimates an even higher CAGR of 6.89% for the period between 2021 and 2028.

These figures reflect the expanding demand for CIP solutions across a wide range of sectors, including finance, government, defense, transportation, logistics, energy, telecommunications, oil and gas, chemicals, manufacturing, and more. The CIP market encompasses both hardware and software solutions, as well as professional and managed services. It includes a diverse array of physical and cybersecurity products and services, such as physical identity systems, access control, perimeter intrusion detection, video surveillance, screening and scanning systems, cybersecurity platforms, encryption, network access controls, firewalls, risk assessment, and threat intelligence solutions.

Prominent vendors, including those with a strong presence in the European market, are actively contributing to this dynamic sector. Their offerings and market roles were also highlighted in previous analyses.

Market Drivers

- **CIP as a Strategic Priority for Governments and Policy Makers:** CIP is at the very top of the political and strategic agendas of most countries worldwide and it is acknowledged as national priority by most countries. This is also the case in the EU, where the European Program for Critical Infrastructure Protection (EPCIP) [15], underlines the CIP's importance for EU-27.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** New CIP related regulations in the EU (such as the CER) directive introduce the need for more and more advanced CIP solutions, as well as related investments in technology and processes. Beyond CIP related regulations (e.g. NIS2, CER, GDPR) there are sectors (e.g. finance, energy) with stringent regulatory compliance requirements, which ask for increased resilience of critical entities.
- **Rapid Urbanization:** Global urbanization trends (including smart city trends) have resulted in a proliferation of critical infrastructure elements in modern cities, but also in a rise in their complexity. The protection and maintenance of infrastructures like transport, energy, telecommunications, and water are nowadays directly linked to the citizens' well-being. This gives rise to additional investments in CIP/CIR solutions.
- **Technology Acceleration:** The accelerated adoption of technologies like artificial intelligence creates new challenges for critical infrastructures and their resilience. This drives investments in CIP/CIR to confront related threats, especially in the cybersecurity landscape.
- **Post COVID19 Trends (Supply Chain Resilience):** The COVID19 pandemic outbreak affected critical infrastructures in various sectors, through indicating their vulnerabilities in the light of large-scale value chain disruptions. Following the end of the pandemic, industrial organizations are more committed to invest in CIP solutions that strengthen the resilience of their critical infrastructures and supply chain.

- **Post COVID19 Trends (Remote Work):** COVID19 has also accelerated the trends of flexible and remote working. The latter require updates to the IT infrastructures that support remote work, including updates to their cybersecurity capabilities in support of work trends like Bring Your Own Device (BYOD). In general, the increased digitalization of business processes coupled with remote work and work from home trends drive the demand for stronger CIP/CIR solutions.
- **International Cyber-Warfare:** The recent war in Ukraine has unveiled the increased significance of cyberwars in warfare. This asks for improved and better solutions to protect critical infrastructures (including defence sector infrastructures) from cyber-attacks.
- **Increased Investments in the Security Skills:** There is a proclaimed gap in security (notably in cybersecurity) skills worldwide, which leads to increased investments in training and skills development services for critical infrastructure security.
- **CIs Maintenance for Continuous Operation:** Maintenance services are expected to be on the rise due to the need to ensure continuous and resilient operation of CIs. This is largely due to the lifespan of Operational Technology (OT) (e.g. 15-25 years), which far exceeds the lifetime of their IT components (e.g. 3-5 years). This makes OT infrastructures vulnerable to cyberattacks and asks for more frequent and systematic maintenance to avoid issues with outdated software.
- **Increased collaboration:** Critical infrastructure operators are also considering investments in collaborative infrastructures for CIP/CIR. This is not only due to regulatory prompts, but is also directly linked with the need to address value chain and supply chain security challenges.
- **Climate Change:** The expected increase of climatic disasters and events due to the on-going climate change is one more driver of the growth of the CIP/CIR market. It challenges critical infrastructures at regional and national scale.

11.2. Annex C.2: Sectorial Whitepapers

Considering the comprehensive insights provided by the produced Whitepapers regarding technological solutions and guidelines across various sectors, a cohesive summary highlights the innovative technologies and guidelines devised to support Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and Resilience within the finance, space, water, telecommunication and transport sectors. This summary draws upon the methodologies, challenges, and advancements discussed in the Whitepapers to emphasize sector-specific approaches and the cross-sectoral application of technologies and practices. The project's whitepapers are publicly accessible via the project's knowledge hub (<https://knowledgehub.euqip.eu/>) and within the project's space in the Zenodo repository/platform (<https://zenodo.org/communities/eu-cip/>).

Figure 10: Classification of Guidelines Elaborated in the Finance Sector Whitepaper.

Finance Sector:

- The EU-CIP finance sector whitepaper presents the main drivers and trends of the CIP/CIR solutions landscape in the finance sector, including for example recent regulatory developments, as well as remote work and digital finance trends. Accordingly, it provides 12 solution guidelines structured in different areas spanning technology development (e.g. AI technology, regulatory support (e.g. CER compliance and financial regulations consideration), training (i.e. employees' and citizens' upskilling), and collaboration (e.g. information sharing). It ends up illustrating a concrete set of recommendations for the effective implementation of these guidelines. The Whitepaper is available through EU-CIP's knowledge hub, as well as within the Zenodo platform [16].

Space Sector:

- The space industry is guided by a holistic security framework integrating cyber and physical security measures. This includes advanced technologies like AI, predictive data analytics, threat detection, and mitigation tools to manage risks to satellite data assets, ground segments, and space systems. Prevention, detection, response, and mitigation technologies for physical and cyber threats are highlighted, alongside the development of robust, accurate, and automated state-of-the-art technologies for comprehensive risk management. The sector's reliance on emerging technologies like drones and quantum communication underscores the evolving landscape of CIP, where innovative solutions are paramount for resilience and security. The Whitepaper is available through EU-CIP's knowledge hub, as well as within the Zenodo platform [17].

Water Sector:

- The water sector's approach involves leveraging digital solutions and tools to secure Digital Water Systems, integrating cyber-physical risk approaches. The STOP-IT project exemplifies the movement towards comprehensive resilience enhancement through collaborative efforts, awareness raising, and competence building. The Digital Water City (DWC) project further illustrates the sector's commitment to secure integration of digital solutions, emphasizing risk management, security recommendations, and best practices for technology providers. The Whitepaper will be soon available through EU-CIP's knowledge hub, as well as within the Zenodo platform.

Telecom and Transport Sectors:

- Both sectors face significant CIP challenges, including cyberattacks, physical threats, natural disasters, and aging infrastructures. The telecom sector focuses on improving situation awareness, securing complex and vulnerable surfaces, and addressing irregularities in supply chains through dynamic threat landscape evaluation, collaborative intelligence gathering, and a zero-trust approach to supply chain security. The transport sector addresses the increasing sophistication of cyberattacks, the use of drones in physical attacks, the impact of climate change, and the challenge of an aging workforce. Solutions include risk assessments, cybersecurity measures, physical security plans, and disaster preparedness and response strategies. The Whitepapers will be soon available through EU-CIP's knowledge hub, as well as within the Zenodo platform.

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